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Deliverable 2.2 Intermediate report on the agroecological impacts of recycling fertiliser application

Closing the gap between fork and farm for circular nutrient flows

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D2.2 – Intermediate report on the agroecological impacts of recycling fertiliser application

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List of abbreviations

BDL	Below detection limit
BOD	Biological oxygen demand
CFU	Colony-forming units
COD	Chemical oxygen demand
Corg	Organic carbon
D	Deliverable
DLC	Dioxin-like compounds
DM	Dry matter
EC	Electrical conductivity
FM	Fresh matter
GHG	Greenhouse gas
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
K	Potassium
M	Month
MPN	Most probable number
N	Nitrogen
Nmin	Mineral nitrogen
Norg	Organic nitrogen
Org-C	Organic carbon
P	Phosphorus
PAH	Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons
PFAS	Polyfluoroalkyl substances
RISE	Research Institutes of Sweden
SAR	Sodium adsorption ratio
Smin	Mineral sulphur
SOP	Standard operating procedure
T	Task
TAMC	Total aerobic microbial count
TDS	Total dissolved solids
TS	Total solids
UWWTD	Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive
VLB	Versuchs- und Lehranstalt für Brauerei
WWTP	Wastewater treatment plant

1 Executive Summary

The focus of **Deliverable 2.2 (interim report)** is to provide the complete data set from **two and a half years** of the field trials set-up in the three pilot regions located on Gotland (Sweden), the North German Plain (Germany) and La Axarquia region (Spain).

Due to the unforeseen delays in the German and Spanish pilot regions (as explained in the Technical Report of Reporting Period 1) it was necessary to extend the duration of Task 2.2 (Monitoring agroecological impacts) up to M44 (instead of M36) in order to organise additional samplings and collect sufficient data to fulfil the requirements specified in the Grant Agreement. This justification and request for extension of Task 2.2 was approved in Amendment No. 4 (AMD-101081883-22).

As agreed with the European Commission, this interim version of D2.2 has been submitted in M36, as it still provides the necessary inputs for other relevant tasks (especially T2.3 – Impact Assessments and T2.4 – Policy interpretation and trade-off analysis).

D2.2 builds on **Deliverable 2.5** (Report on the methods used to determine agroecological impacts) which was submitted in M24 and classified as “sensitive”, that included data from field trials in the three pilot regions collected for **more than one year**. Therefore, D2.2 follows a similar structure and presentation of results, although it has been complemented with additional analyses, such as the risk assessment and sampling optimisation.

All the collected data has been inputted into the data collection sheet developed in T2.1 (Guidelines and criteria for data acquisition and methodology) and uploaded in the P2Green Innovation Platform, enhancing accessibility and understanding of data.

Lastly, D2.2 will be completed with the final results of the monitoring campaign and presented in **Deliverable 2.6** (Report on the agroecological impacts of recycling fertiliser application – final report) classified as “public”, which will combine both D2.5 and D2.2 and will be submitted in M44, coinciding with the end date of Task 2.2 and WP2.

2 Introduction

In this report we further elaborate on the comprehensive list of analysed parameters (already provided in Deliverable 2.5 in M24, sensitive report) including additional parameters monitored during the period M24-M36. The methods and protocols considered for the new parameters have been described, together with the results of the field trials carried out in the three pilot regions until M36.

In relation to the field trials, the agroecological impacts of the new and innovative fertilising products processed from separated urine and dry toilet contents, as well as municipal wastewater (i.e., urine fertiliser, faecal compost, Aurin® and reclaimed water) are further elaborated.

As it is of outstanding importance to specify and detail the procedure to assess the agroecological impacts of using the bio-based fertiliser products in both crops and the environment, different methods and protocols have been applied in each pilot region - as different nutrient sources are used (i.e., urine, faeces, municipal wastewater) and regional and national regulatory requirements vary.

2.1 Task objectives

This interim version of D2.2 belongs to T2.2. The objective of this task is to assess the agroecological effect of the fertiliser products in each pilot region. To achieve this objective, sampling and analyses of processed separated urine and dry solid contents, treated municipal wastewater, soil, leaves and harvested crops have been carried out to monitor and control macro and micronutrient concentrations, presence of pathogens, pharmaceuticals or heavy metals, among other components. Greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions are also monitored.

This comprehensive analysis of different sample matrices will enable a holistic analysis of the agroecological and environmental impacts of the bio-based fertiliser use.

This task is closely related with D2.5 (due in M24), D2.2 (due in M36) and D2.6 (due in M44), as they set the guidelines to carry out all the abovementioned analyses.

3 New data collected from M24 to M36

As described in D2.5, the selection of parameters analysed and monitored in P2GreenN is driven by a combination of regulatory compliance, scientific best practices, and project-specific objectives.

Adhering to local, regional and international regulations ensures safety and sustainability. Utilising established methodologies and risk assessment tools guarantees data reliability and identifies potential risks. Moreover, monitoring key parameters aligns with the project goals, supports data-driven decision-making, and contributes to scientific knowledge.

In this chapter 3, we refer to **new parameters and data collected in the three pilot regions** from **M24 to M36**, as opposed to D2.5 that described parameters monitored from the beginning of field trials in M4 until M24.

In 3.1 sub-chapter, we provide a justification for the analysis and monitoring of new parameters per pilot region, whereas in 3.2 sub-chapter, we have included a list of parameters considered in each pilot region per category: fertilising product, harvested crop, soil, environmental pollution and GHG emissions.

3.1 Justification for analysis and monitoring of new selected parameters

The nature and concept of the selected fertilisers per pilot region makes necessary to adapt the parameters to be measured over time. In this sense, some parameters apply to solid fertilisers while other parameters must be analysed while dealing with treated wastewater, for example.

- **Swedish pilot region**

In addition to the parameters monitored from M4-M24, during the new period M24-M36 we also tracked a targeted suite of pharmaceutical residues along the whole production chain - from urine-derived fertiliser through irrigation water and soil to harvested crops and the final beer - to evaluate performance and safety of the circular fertilisation approach. The analyses were selected a priori using four criteria: (i) high consumption and frequent detection in urine/wastewater in Europe (e.g., antihypertensives such as valsartan, irbesartan and losartan; beta-blockers such as metoprolol and propranolol; antibiotics including clarithromycin, clindamycin, sulfamethoxazole and trimethoprim); (ii) environmental relevance spanning persistence and mobility (e.g., carbamazepine and hydrochlorothiazide as conservative tracers; more degradable or sorbing compounds such as sertraline and fluoxetine), (iii) toxicological and food-safety relevance for potential plant uptake and carry-over to food and beverages (e.g., venlafaxine and its metabolite N,O-didesmethylvenlafaxine; antihistamines such as cetirizine and fexofenadine), and (iv) analytical robustness across all matrices. This balanced panel covers multiple therapeutic classes and physicochemical behaviours, allowing us to trace removal/transformation, plant uptake, and any transfer to beer. The results provide field-

scale evidence to support informed decisions on nutrient recovery, food safety, and the future of circular agriculture.

- **German pilot region**

Overall, the set of parameters analysed in the German pilot region from M24 to M36 was the same as from M4 to M24. However, the monitoring of recycling fertilisers was extended following the implementation of faecal composting by Goldeimer (GE) in Ollsen and Aurin® production by VunaNexus (VN) at the Kreiswerke Barnim (KWB) pilot site in Eberswalde. Additional samples were taken from input materials and intermediate products during recycling fertiliser production to better assess the treatment process itself, in particular regarding the inactivation of pathogens but also the degradation of organic pollutants. Because the GHG emission measurements from the 2024 trial with mustard were inconclusive, a new trial was setup with zucchini plants at IGZ to gather more data on GHG emissions after recycling fertiliser application.

- **Spanish pilot region**

Besides the parameters considered during the first monitoring period (M4-M24) in the Spanish pilot region, analyses of pharmaceutical compounds in reclaimed water, as well as in secondary treated wastewater, local well water, soil water, leaves from avocado and mango trees, and mango fruits have been carried out during M24-M36 to monitor the influence of reclaimed water use in agriculture. Criteria such as the presence of pharmaceuticals compounds in surface and groundwater bodies, relevance of selected parameters in the new UWWTD, and the impact on antimicrobial resistance, has been considered for the selection and analysis of specific pharmaceuticals. Also, as mango fruits were sampled for the first time in August (M33) and September 2025 (M34), some fruits have been analysed for fruit quality parameters, which are of outstanding importance for the end user.

3.2 List of new parameters analysed and monitored

The next paragraphs include the considered parameters listed per category and type of sample in each pilot region during the period from M24 to M36.

- **Swedish pilot region**

Urine fertiliser: the processed urine fertiliser was analysed before being used as fertiliser (M4, M16 and M29) for total nitrogen (%), urea (%), phosphate (%), ammonium (%), chloride (%), calcium (%), magnesium (%), potassium (%), sulphate (%), total carbon (%) and, organic carbon (%).

Harvested crops: the harvested barley crop (straw, barley's grain) was analysed for the following in M10, M24 and M35: total nitrogen (g/kg), calcium (g/kg), potassium (g/kg), magnesium (g/kg), sodium (g/kg), phosphorus (g/kg), sulphur (g/kg), copper (g/kg), iron (g/kg), manganese (g/kg), zinc (g/kg), yield (kg/ha), straw strength/breaking, field weight

(before/after cleaning), water content (%), protein (%), starch (%), space weight (g/L), ergosterol, purity (%), malting grain sorting, pure weight fact (TS).

Soil: samples were taken at two depths (0-30 cm and 30-60 cm) before (M5, M17 and M21) and after (M9, M29 and M34) the growth season and analysed (M1, 24 and 35) for the following parameters: moisture content (TS, %), NH₄-N (mg/100gTS), NH₄-N (kg/ha), NO₃-N (mg/100gTS), NO₃-N (kg/ha), N-min (kg/ha), pH, phosphorus (mg/100g), potassium (mg/100g), magnesium (mg/100g), calcium (mg/100g), potassium (mg/100g), aluminum (mg/100g), iron (mg/100g), potassium (mg/100g), copper (mg/kg), total carbon (g/kg), total nitrogen (g/kg).

Beer production (entire production chain): pharmaceuticals residues were analysed (M24 and M36) for all matrices: urine fertiliser, harvested crops, soil, water (irrigation, beer production) and beer. A total of 40 parameters were analysed.

Table 1: Sampling schedule and measured parameters from the Swedish pilot region for urine fertiliser, harvested crops and soil from the field trial during M24-M36.

Sampling date	Sample type	Measured parameters		
M29	Urine fertiliser	N P K S Ca Cl ⁻	Mg Ammonium Urea Nitrate Phosphate	Total carbon Organic carbon pH EC
M24, M35	Harvested crops	Yield (untreated) Relative number Yield (water adjusted) Number of plants Number of shoots	Malting grain sorting Number of ears Straw strength Space weight Purity Pure weight fact	Mass per 500 g Water content Protein Emergence energy Starch Protein Ergosterol
M29, M34	Soil	Moisture content Ammonium (NH ₄ -N) Nitrate (NO ₃ -N) pH EC Total carbon TS	Organic carbon Totan nitrogen N-min K Na Ca Mg	P Mn Na Titratable acidity Al Fe Cu
M24, M36	Urine fertiliser, soil, water (irrigation, beer production), harvest crops, beer	Pharmaceuticals: Bicalutamide, Bisoprolol, Candesartan, Carbamazepine, Cetirizine, Chloramphenicol, Citalopram, Clarithromycin, Clindamycin, Desvenlafaxine, Diazepam, Diclofenac, Diltiazem, Fexofenadine, Fluoxetine, Furosemide, Gemfibrozil, Hydrochlorothiazide, Irbesartan, Lamotrigine, Losartan, Memantine, Metoprolol, Metronidazole, N,O-didesmethylvenlafaxine, Oxazepam, Propranolol, Salicylic Acid, Sertraline, Sotalol, Sulfamethoxazole, Telmisartan, Trimethoprim, Valsartan, Venlafaxine, Verapamil		

- **German pilot region**

Recycling fertilisers: The input material for faecal composting, i.e. hygienised dry toilet contents, was analysed for pathogens (i.e., *E. coli*, *Salmonella*, *Enterococcus* and *Clostridium perfringens*; expressed as MPN/g FM, CFU/g FM or findings in 50 g FM) and total aerobic microbial count (CFU/g FM) as general process parameter. The same analyses were done on intermediate samples taken from the Earthflow container during the composting process and on the final compost prior to field application. Samples from hygienised dry toilet contents were also taken for analysis of macronutrients (% DM or mg/kg FM), micronutrients (% DM), organic matter content (% DM), heavy metals (mg/kg DM), per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS; mg/kg DM), polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs; mg/kg DM), and pharmaceuticals. Dioxins and dioxin-like compounds, were not further considered for the GE compost, as they pose no particular risk based on the exchange with German authorities and their analysis is expensive. However, a few more general quality parameters were included. The self-heating ability (°C) and degree of composition (I-V) were analysed as additional indicators for the maturity and stability of compost. The content of germinable plant parts/seeds (plants/L) was added as an indicator for phytohygiene. Stones > 10 mm (% DM) and foreign materials > 1 mm (% DM) were used to assess contamination with macroscopic particles that couldn't be removed during the sieving process. The Aurin® fertiliser produced by VN was analysed for macro- and micronutrients (% or mg/L) heavy metals (mg/L), pathogens and per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS; mg/L), and pharmaceuticals. The same analyses were conducted at the input material (percolated urine from dry toilets) and the filtered intermediate product (nitrified and filtered urine).

Harvested crops: Shoots from the field trial with buckwheat were sampled in M35 to determine the yield of fresh biomass (dt/ha) and dry biomass (g m⁻²). A separate sampling of buckwheat grains wasn't done, because the growth of buckwheat and weeds was very heterogeneous across the field site, with some of the test plots including almost no buckwheat plants. For the same reason, the selection of quality parameters will be based on the use of the shoots as silage, with the details still to be clarified. Subsamples from the recycling fertiliser plots were frozen at -20 °C to allow for a pharmaceutical screening if pharmaceutical substances are detected in the GE compost.

Table 2Soil: Soil from the trial with buckwheat was sampled before fertilisation and at harvest for Nmin analysis at three depths (0–30 cm, 30–60 cm and 60–90 cm). Other macro- and micronutrients in 0–30 cm and 30–60 cm depth were only analysed at harvest, using mixed samples for each treatment from all four plots per treatment for cost efficiency. An intermediate sampling during the growing season was not conducted, as the buckwheat trial was only fertilised once due to the shorter growing season. Subsamples from the recycling fertiliser plots were frozen at -20 °C to allow for a pharmaceutical screening if pharmaceutical substances are detected in the GE compost.

Table 2: Sampling schedule and measured parameters from the German pilot region for recycling fertiliser, soil, and crops from the field trial during M24-M36.

Trial	Sampling date	Sample type	Measured parameters		
Faecal composting in Ollsen	M28	Hygienised dry toilet contents	<i>E. coli, Salmonella, Enterococcus, Clostridium perfringens</i> Total aerobic microbial count		
	M35		Dry matter & organic content, basic-active ingredients, pH, chloride, salt content, total C, N (total, NH ₄ , NO ₃), P (total, soluble), K, Mg, S, Ca, B, Co, Fe, Cu, Mn, Mo, Se, Zn, Na Heavy metals (As, Pb, Cd, Cr, Ni, Hg, Tl)	<i>E. coli</i> <i>Salmonella</i> <i>Enterococcus</i> <i>Clostridium perfringens</i> Total aerobic microbial count Foreign materials (stones, plastics, glass, metal)	PFAS PAHs Carbamazepine Carithromycin Ciprofloxacin Diclofenac Ethinylestradiol/ Estradiol
	M29, M32	Faecal compost	<i>E. coli, Salmonella, Enterococcus, Clostridium perfringens</i> Total aerobic microbial count		
	M31		Dry matter & organic content, basic-active ingredients, pH, chloride, salt content, total C, N (total, NH ₄ , NO ₃), P (total, soluble), K, Mg, S, Ca, B, Co, Fe, Cu, Mn, Mo, Se, Zn, Na Heavy metals (As, Pb, Cd, Cr, Ni, Hg, Tl)	<i>E. coli</i> <i>Salmonella</i> <i>Enterococcus</i> <i>Clostridium perfringens</i> Foreign materials (stones, plastics, glass, metal) Degree of decay Germinable seeds and plant parts	PFAS PAHs Carbamazepine Carithromycin Ciprofloxacin Diclofenac Ethinylestradiol/ Estradiol
Field trial at Vagtshoff	M32	Imported Aurin®	Chloride, N (total, NH ₄ , NO ₃), P (total, soluble), K, Mg, S, Ca, B, Co, Fe, Cu, Mn, Mo, Se, Zn, Na Heavy metals (As, Pb, Cd, Cr, Ni, Hg, Tl)	<i>E. coli</i> <i>Salmonella</i> <i>Enterococcus</i> <i>Clostridium perfringens</i> Total aerobic count	PFAS Carbamazepine Carithromycin Ciprofloxacin Diclofenac Ethinylestradiol/ Estradiol
	M35	Buckwheat biomass	Fresh weight Dry weight Total carbon Total nitrogen	Protein content Starch content	Nutrients (B, Ca, Cu, Fe, K, Mg, Mn, Mo, Na, P, S, Zn)
	M29, M35	Soil	Moisture content Soil type Soil pH	Ammonium, nitrate, P, K, Mg, Mn, Cu, Zn, Na, B	Total carbon Organic carbon Total nitrogen
Urine treatment at KWB	M36	Stored urine	Chloride, N (total, NH ₄ , NO ₃), P (total, soluble), K, Mg, S, Ca, B, Co, Fe, Cu, Mn, Mo, Se, Zn, Na	<i>E. coli</i> <i>Salmonella</i> <i>Enterococcus</i> <i>Clostridium perfringens</i> Total aerobic count	PFAS Carbamazepine Carithromycin Ciprofloxacin
		Nitrified urine			
		Produced Aurin®			

			Heavy metals (As, Pb, Cd, Cr, Ni, Hg, Tl)		Diclofenac Ethinylestradiol/ Estradiol
IGZ Zucchini trial	M29-M34	Soil	Greenhouse gas emission measurements (N ₂ O, CO ₂ , CH ₄)		
	M34	Zucchini shoot and fruit biomass	Fresh weight Dry weight Total carbon Total nitrogen	Plant growth dynamics and marketable fruit yield over the growing season	Nutrients (B, Ca, Cu, Fe, K, Mg, Mn, Mo, Na, P, S, Zn)
	M29, M32 M34	Soil	Moisture content Soil type Soil pH	Ammonium, nitrate, P, K, Mg, Mn, Cu, Zn, Na, B	Total carbon Organic carbon Total nitrogen

- **Spanish pilot region**

Recycling fertiliser (reclaimed water): key parameters are regularly analysed since M4 in two water sources interacting in the field trial (i.e., reclaimed water and local well water). These include basic physicochemical parameters, such as EC ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$), water temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), pH, turbidity (NFU), total dissolved solids (TDS – mg/l -), BOD₅ (mg/l) or COD (mg/l). Most parameters are measured on a monthly basis except, for instance, BOD₅ and COD (measured weekly). Another group of parameters measured on a monthly basis are macronutrients (N, Total P, Ca, Mg, K, Na – mg/l -), micronutrients (Fe, S, B, Mn - $\mu\text{g}/\text{l}$ -), ammonium (mg/l), anions (Cl, sulphate, bicarbonate, carbonate – mg/l -), SAR (sodium adsorption ratio), and heavy metals (As, Be, Cd, Co, Cr, Cu, Mo, Ni, Se, V). Pathogens (*Escherichia coli* – $\text{CFU}/100 \text{ ml}$ -, *Legionella* spp – CFU/ml -, nematodes –units) are measured on a weekly basis.

In addition to regular water sampling, water probes and a data logger Hach® are installed in a measurement tank where reclaimed water is stored and distributed for irrigation of crops. This data logger is recording EC, pH, T°, turbidity, Cl, K, nitrate and ammonium parameters in 30-minute intervals.

With regards to pharmaceuticals analysis in reclaimed water, a first sampling campaign has been performed in M33 (August 2025), and a second campaign is planned for M39 (February 2026). For comparative analysis, sampling in reclaimed water is complemented with analysis in local well water and secondary treated wastewater, as well as from lysimeters. The following emerging and pharmaceutical compounds were analysed in these samples: Carbamazepine, Diclofenac, Clarithromycin, Azithromycin, Sulfamethoxazole, Norfloxacin, Gabapentin, Iopromide, Atrazine, Chlorpyrifos, Metoprolol, Venlafaxine, Losartan, Ciprofloxacin, Ciprofloxacin, Tramadol, Clindamycin, Erythromycin and Lincomycin.

Harvested crops: the following emerging and pharmaceutical compounds were analysed in mango and avocado leaves, as well as in mango fruits taken in M33: Carbamazepine, Diclofenac, Clarithromycin, Azithromycin, Sulfamethoxazole, Norfloxacin, Gabapentin, Iopromide, Atrazine, Chlorpyrifos, Metoprolol, Venlafaxine, Losartan, Ciprofloxacin, Ciprofloxacin, Tramadol, Clindamycin, Erythromycin and Lincomycin.

In addition, several mango fruit quality parameters have been analysed in M33: dry matter (%), net weight (gr), Brix grades, acidity (%), maturity index, firmness (kgf/cm²), colour, diameter, longitude, [Cd, Pb, Hg, Ni (mg/kg)] and pesticides.

Besides these analyses, another two foliar analysis sampling campaign were conducted in M24 and M32 to monitor the influence of reclaimed water on mango and avocado leaves.

Soil: a soil sample was carried out in M25 to continue the monitoring of the below-mentioned parameters.

Table 3: Sampling schedule and measured parameters from the Spanish pilot region for reclaimed water, local well water, leaves and soil from the field trial during M24-M36.

Sampling date	Sample type	Measured parameters		
Monthly (*weekly) (**bi-weekly)	Reclaimed water	EC Temperature pH Turbidity TDS SAR N Total P Ca Mg Nitrate Ammonium K Na	Cl Sulphate Bicarbonate Carbonate Fe S B Mn TSS* BOD ₅ * COD* <i>E. coli</i> * <i>Legionella spp</i> ** Nematodes**	As Be Cd Co Cr Cu Mo Ni Se V Zn
Monthly	Well water	EC Temperature pH Turbidity TDS SAR N Total P Ca Mg Nitrate	K Na Ammonium Cl Sulphate Bicarbonate Carbonate Fe S B Mn	As Be Cd Co Cr Cu Mo Ni Se V Zn
M24, M32	Mango and avocado leaves	Mg Ca K P	N Cl Na B Mn	Cu Zn Fe Mo
M25	Soil	Soil humidity pH EC Organic carbon	Equivalent calcium carbonate N-NO ₃ P K	Mg Na Ca/Mg Mg/K Ca/K

		Organic matter Active limestone	Ca	Soil texture
M33	Secondary treated wastewater Reclaimed and well water Lysimeters Mango and avocado leaves Mango fruits	Carbamazepine Diclofenac Clarithromycin Azithromycin Sulfamethoxazole Norfloxacin Gabapentin	Iopromide Atrazine Chlorpyrifos Metoprolol Venlafaxine Losartan	Ciprofloxacin Omeprazole Tramadol Clindamycin Erythromycin Lincomycin
M33	Mango fruits	Dry matter Net weight Brix grades Acidity Maturity index	Firmness Colour Diameter Longitude Pesticides	Cd Pb Hg Ni

4 Methodology for sampling and analysis of new parameters

In this chapter, the methodology and protocols considered for the sampling and analyses of the new parameters (presented in chapter 3) are described in detail for each pilot region.

- **Swedish pilot region**

The data collection for the field trials in the Swedish pilot region was conducted according to a structured sampling and analytical protocol, ensuring methodological consistency across all sampling campaigns. The applied methods and corresponding standards are summarised in **Table 4**.

The processed urine fertiliser produced within the Swedish pilot region (**Figure 1**) was analysed prior to field application (M4, M16 and M29). The analyses were performed using a *Thermo Scientific™ Gallery™ discrete analyser* located at the Department of Energy and Technology, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (SLU). This instrument was employed to determine the concentrations of urea and major ions in the liquid fertiliser (C) and nitrogen (N) contents of the soil samples were quantified through dry combustion in accordance with ISO 10694 (1995) and ISO 13878 (1998), respectively, using an elemental analyser for macro-samples (*TruMac® CN, Leco Corp., St Joseph, MI, USA*). Soil pH and electrical conductivity (EC) were determined following ISO 10390:2007 and EN 15933:2012. These analyses provided the baseline and post-harvest parameters necessary to evaluate soil fertility, nutrient dynamics, and potential environmental effects of the applied fertilisers.

Figure 1: Processed urine fertiliser produced within the Swedish pilot region.

The harvested barley crop (**Figure 2**) was subjected to comprehensive post-harvest analysis (M10, M24 and M35). Samples were divided into two matrices—straw and grain—and analysed by Agrilab AB, a certified agricultural testing laboratory. Additional

analyses were performed by Hushållningssällskapet Gotland, focusing on agronomic quality parameters relevant for feed and brewing applications.

Figure 2: Barley crops and harvesting process in the Swedish pilot region.

Soil sampling was coordinated and managed by Hushållningssällskapet and carried out at two depths (0–30 cm and 30–60 cm), representing the topsoil and subsoil layers. Sampling was undertaken both before the sowing season (M5 and M17) and after harvest (M9, M21, and M34). The collected soil samples were analysed at Agrilab AB (M12 and M24), ensuring accredited laboratory procedures and traceable quality control.

In addition, pharmaceutical residue sampling was implemented to assess potential micropollutant transfer within the agricultural and processing chain. Samples were collected from soil, irrigation water, water used in beer production, harvested barley, and final beer products (M24 and M36). The analyses were carried out by the Water Department at the Institute for Water and Environment (IVM/SLU), accredited for pharmaceutical analysis. A targeted LC-MS/MS method was applied to quantify 40 pharmaceutical compounds under controlled analytical conditions. The system comprised a *DIONEX UltiMate 3000 UPLC* (Thermo Scientific) coupled to a *TSQ Quantiva triple quadrupole mass spectrometer* (Thermo Scientific). Chromatographic separation was achieved using an *Acquity UPLC BEH C-18 column* (100 mm × 2.1 mm i.d., 1.7 µm

particle size; Waters Corp.) maintained at 40 °C. The mobile phases consisted of (a) Milli-Q water with 5 mM ammonium acetate and (b) acetonitrile, with a constant flow rate of 0.5 mL min⁻¹. Different sample matrices were prepared using tailored pre-treatment methods: water samples by *solid-phase extraction*, dried-urine fertiliser and beer samples by *direct injection*, and soil and plant samples by *solvent extraction*. This matrix-specific approach ensured reliable detection limits and robust quantification across all investigated environmental compartments.

Table 4: Methods used for the laboratory analyses of the parameters measured in the Swedish pilot region, including new ones.

Matrix	Parameters	Methods
Soil	Moisture content, Ammonium (NH ₄ -N), Nitrate (NO ₃ -N), pH, EC, Total-carbon, Organic carbon, Tot-Nan nitrogen, K, Na, Ca, Mg, P, Mn, Na, Titratable acidity	ISO 10694:1995; ISO 13878:1998; EN ISO 10390:2022, SS-ISO 11265:1996 with the following equipment: Autoanalyzer, Metrohm 855 Robotic Titrosampler, Konduktivitetmätare VWR MU 6100 L, LECO Trumac CN, ICP-OES Avio
Crop	Yield (untreated)	Measured by combine harvester machine during harvest
	Number of plants, Number of shoots, Number of ears, Straw strength	Manual counting in random section of 1 m ² per treatment
	Pharmaceutical residues (if detected in fertiliser)	LC-MS/MS
	Relative number, Yield (water adjusted)	Oven for dry weight of 500 g grain and calculation
Urine fertiliser	Pharmaceutical residues	LC-MS/MS
	Urea	The difference between ammonia determination with and without enzymatic conversion by urease.
	Ammonium (as N)	Reaction with hypochlorite ions, salicylate ions and sodium nitroprusside.
	Phosphate	Reaction with ammonium molybdate, antimony potassium tartrate and ascorbic acid.
	Chloride	Reaction with mercury (II) thiocyanate.
	Nitrate (as N)	Reaction with hydrazine, sulphanilamide and N-1naphthylethylenediamine dihydrochloride.

- **German pilot region**

An overview of the methods used for the agroecological monitoring in the German pilot region can be found in **Table 5**. Soil samples taken in M21 from the field trial with rye were analysed for their total C content, total N content, C/N ratio, and organic C (Corg) content using elemental analysis at the IGZ. The organic N (Norg) content was calculated as difference between total N and Nmin that was analysed before (cf. D2.5 – Fig. 8), assuming that nitrite contents in soil were negligible. In 2025, soil samples were taken on all 16 plots from the field trial with buckwheat in April (M29) and October (M35) using an automated sampling system that was mounted at the back of an off-road vehicle. The advantage of the automated sampling system is that the sampling is much faster and comes with a higher precision as the pneumatic auger reduces soil compaction during sampling and ensures always the same insertion depth. In M29, 48 soil samples (0-30 cm, 30-60 cm, and 60-90 cm) were analysed for Nmin to assess the initial situation before fertilisation and to adjust the amount of fertiliser to be applied later based on plant N demand. Another 48 soil samples were taken for Nmin analysis at the time of harvest (M35) to determine the remaining N in soil and to assess potential leaching to deeper soil layers. These samples will also be analysed for total C, total N, C/N, and Corg. In M35, also samples for general soil parameters/other nutrients were taken as mixed samples (n=4) from each fertiliser treatment (0-30 cm and 30-60 cm). Soil samples for Nmin and for general soil parameters/other nutrients were sent to the external lab Agrolab (Leinefelde, Germany).

Samples were taken from the hygienised dry toilet contents (M28 and M35), pre-mature compost (M29), and the final compost product (M31 and M32) for analysing hygiene parameters. For the hygienised dry toilet contents and the pre-mature compost, representative samples were gained by taking subsamples at different positions and depths within the pile/Earthflow container and combining them to a mixed sample. The sampling of the final compost product was done following a guideline developed within the zirkulierBAR project. Samples were taken during the sieving process, by placing 30 L buckets below the sieve to collect the sieved material (**Figure 3** - left). In total, 6 buckets were filled to half and afterwards combined to a mixed sample. Because the volume of the mixed sample was larger than what was needed for the analysis, the sample volume was reduced following a stepwise sequence. First, the mixed sample was put on a tarpaulin and divided with a spade into four equal sections (**Figure 3** - right). Then, one of the sections was removed and the remaining material was mixed. The remaining material was again divided into four equal sections, and one part was removed. This process continued until the amount of sample needed for analysis was left. The samples were either sent to LUFA Nord-West (Oldenburg, Germany) or jenaBios GmbH (Jena, Germany) for the analysis of hygiene parameters (pathogens), main nutrients, general quality parameters, pharmaceuticals, PFAS, PAHs, heavy metals and foreign materials. The Aurin[®] fertiliser used for the field trial in 2025 was sampled in M35 to determine its exact composition. A sample was taken from each of the two IBCs that were delivered to the Vagthoff by VN. The samples were sent to jenaBios GmbH (Jena, Germany) for the

analysis of hygiene parameters (pathogens), main nutrients, pharmaceuticals, PFAS, and heavy metals.

Figure 3: Sampling of the first GE compost batch produced in M31. Left: Sample collection with bucket placed under the vibration sieve. Right: Mixed sample from six buckets and volume reduction on a tarpaulin.

Plant samples from the field trial with rye in 2024 and the greenhouse trial with kohlrabi in 2024 were analysed for their total C content, total N content and C/N ratio at IGZ. The total N content ($\text{kg}_N \text{kg}^{-1}$) was used to calculate plant N uptake ($\text{kg}_N \text{ha}^{-1}$) in different plant parts by multiplying the previously determined dry biomass (kg ha^{-1}) with the newly measured total N content. From the field trial with buckwheat in 2025, shoot biomass was sampled from each of the 16 plots by collecting the total aboveground biomass from three representative quadrats with 1 m^2 each. This was done by cutting the shoots in the 100 cm by 100 cm quadrats as close to soil as possible (**Figure 4**). Samples were placed in paper bags and the fresh weight was recorded. Afterwards, samples were dried in a drying oven at $70 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for an average of five days until a constant weight was achieved, at which point the dry weight was measured and recorded. Biomass per square meter was then calculated using the recorded weights and the total quadrat area per plot (3 m^2). These samples will also be used to analyse total C content, total N content and C/N ratio. Additional shoot samples were collected from the recycling fertiliser plots and frozen at $-20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for later analysis of pharmaceuticals and quality parameters.

Figure 4: Sampling of shoot biomass in the field trial with buckwheat at Vagtshoff.

To gather more data on the recycling fertiliser efficiency and the greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions associated with the combined application of faecal compost and Aurin[®], a field trial with zucchini plants (*Cucurbita pepo* var. Diamant F1) was conducted at the IGZ from M30 to M34 (**Figure 5**). In the experiment, four different fertiliser treatments were used: No fertiliser (control), recycling fertilisers (faecal compost provided by Finizio GmbH and Aurin[®] provided by VN), conventional mineral fertilisers (Osmocote Pro 3-4 M and calcium ammonium nitrate), and cattle slurry from a nearby agricultural cooperation as conventional organic fertiliser. Because the nitrous oxide (N₂O) fluxes were often below the detection limit of the gas chromatograph systems in the previous field trial with mustard, different gas sampling chambers were used in the zucchini trial. For the used rectangular chambers, the ratio of the covered soil surface area to chamber volume is higher compared to the round cylindrical chambers used in the mustard trial. In theory, this should lead to higher enrichment of N₂O concentrations over the sampling time, and thus facilitate the quantification of GHG emissions. However, the evaluation of measured data is ongoing and the final results will be included in D2.6.

Figure 5: Design of the field trial with zucchini plants conducted at the IGZ (left), and photographs from the trial in M30 (right, top) and M33 (right, bottom) with rectangular chambers that were used for GHG emission measurements.

Table 5: Updated methods used for the laboratory analyses of the parameters measured in soil, crop biomass, and recycling fertilisers in the German pilot region.

Matrix	Parameters	Methods
Soil	Dry matter content	VDLUFA I, A 2.1.1: 1991
	Nmin (NH ₄ -N + NO ₃ -N)	VDLUFA I, A 6.1.4.1: 2002
	Smin (SO ₄ -S)	VDLUFA I, A 6.3.1: 2016
	pH	VDLUFA I, A 5.1.1: 2016 (CaCl ₂)
	Phosphorus (P ₂ O ₅), Potassium (K ₂ O)	VDLUFA I, A 6.2.1.2 DL: 1991
	Mg	VDLUFA I, A 6.2.4.1: 1991
	Mn, Cu, Zn, Na, B	VDLUFA I, A 6.4.1: 2002
	Total carbon, Organic carbon, Total nitrogen	Elemental analyser (Elemental Combustion System, CHNS-O)
Crop biomass	Pharmaceutical residues (if detected in fertiliser): screening of 99 substances, quantification of Carbamazepine, Carithromycin, Ciprofloxacin, Diclofenac, Ethinylestradiol/Estradiol, Tetracyclines	HA JB 302, 2021-04; HPLC-MS/MS
	Total carbon, Total nitrogen	Elemental analyser (Elemental Combustion System, CHNS-O)
	Pathogens: <i>Clostridium perfringens</i>	LUFA Nord-West 1/3-515: 2022-11
	Pharmaceutical residues (if detected in fertiliser): screening of 99 substances,	HA JB 302, 2021-04; HPLC-MS/MS

	quantification of Carbamazepine, Carithromycin, Ciprofloxacin, Diclofenac, Ethinylestradiol/Estradiol, Tetracyclines	
	Dry matter content	Oven
	Quality parameters (starch, protein)	VO (EG) 152 Anhang III: 2009
Faecal compost / hygienised dry toilet contents	Electrical conductivity	DIN EN 13038: 2000-02
	Dry Matter	DIN EN 15934: 2012-11 or DIN EN 13040: 2007-02
	Organic matter	DIN EN 15935: 2012-11 or DIN EN 13039: 2000-02
	Total N	DIN EN 16169: 2012-11
	Ammonium Nitrogen (NH ₄ -N)	DIN EN ISO 11732-E 23: 2005-05 or DIN 38406-5-2: 1983-10
	Nitrate Nitrogen (NO ₃ -N)	DIN EN ISO 13395-D 28: 1996-12
	Available Nitrogen (NH ₄ -N + NO ₃ -N)	calculated from NH ₄ -N and NO ₃ -N
	Phosphorus (P ₂ O ₅), mineral acid soluble	DIN EN ISO 11885 (E 22): 2009-09 (mod.), #A1 or DIN EN ISO 17294-2 (2005) [L93]
	Phosphorus (P ₂ O ₅), water soluble	VDLUFA I, A 6.2.1.1: 2016 or DIN EN ISO 17294-2: 2017-01
	Potassium (K ₂ O)	DIN EN ISO 17294-2 (2005) [L93]
	As, Pb, Cd, Cr, Cu, Ni, Hg, Zn, B, Co, Fe, Mn, Mo, Ca, Mg, Na, S	DIN EN ISO 11885: 2009-09
	Tl, Se	DIN EN ISO 17294-2: 2017-01
	Chloride	DIN EN ISO 10304-1 (D20) 2009-07 [L80]
	Basic Active Components (as CaO)	VDLUFA II.1, 6.3.2: 2008 or BGK, III. B2.1 (9/2006) (N)
	pH	VDLUFA I, A 5.1.1: 2016 or DIN EN 13037: 2000-02
	Salt Content	VDLUFA I, A 10.1.1: 1991 or DIN EN 13038: 2000-02
	Self-heating	BGK Kap. IV A1: 2006-09; #6
	Degree of decomposition	BGK Kap. IV A1: 2006-09; #6
	Germinable plant parts/seeds	BGK Kap. IV B1: 2006-09; #5
	Stones > 10 mm	BGK Kap. II. C2.1: 2013-05; #1
	Foreign materials > 1 mm	BGK Kap. II. C1.1/C1.2: 2020-04; #1
	Total aerobic microbial count	BGK Kap. IV C2: 2006-09; #1 or ASU L 00.00-88: 2015-06, DIN EN ISO 4833-2: 2014-05 (F)
	<i>Clostridium perfringens</i>	ASU L 00.00-57, DIN EN ISO 7937 (F)
	<i>Escherichia coli</i> (Fäkalcoliforme Bakterien)	BGK Kap. IV C3: 2006-09; #1 or DIN 38411 (F)
	<i>Enterococcaceae</i> (Fäkalstreptokokken)	BGK Kap. IV C4: 2006-09; #1 or DIN 7899-2 (F)
	<i>Salmonella spp.</i>	BGK Kap. IV C1: 2013-05; #1

	Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS): PFOS/PFOA	DIN 38414-14: 2011-08
	Polycyclic aromatic, hydrocarbons (PAHs; EPA 16)	DIN ISO 13877: 2000-01, Verfahren B or DIN ISO 18287: 2006-05, Variante B
	Pharmaceutical residues: screening of 99 substances, quantification of Carbamazepine, Carithromycin, Ciprofloxacin, Diclofenac, Ethinylestradiol/Estradiol, Tetracyclines	HA JB 302, 2021-04; HPLC- MS/MS
Aurin® / nitrified urine / stored urine	Total N	DIN EN 16169: 2012-11
	Ammonium Nitrogen (NH ₄ -N)	DIN 38406-5-2: 1983-10
	Nitrate Nitrogen (NO ₃ -N)	DIN EN ISO 13395-D 28: 1996-12
	Phosphorus (P ₂ O ₅), total content	DIN EN ISO 17294-2 (2005) [L93]
	Phosphorus (P ₂ O ₅), water soluble	DIN EN ISO 17294-2:2017-01
	Potassium oxide (K ₂ O)	DIN EN ISO 17294-2 (2005) [L93]
	As, Pb, Cd, Cr, Cu, Ni, Hg, Zn, B, Co, Fe, Mn, Mo, Ca, Mg, Na, S	DIN EN ISO 11885: 2009-09
	Tl, Se	DIN EN ISO 17294-2: 2017-01
	Chloride	DIN EN ISO 10304-1 (D20): 2009- 07 [L80]
	Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS): PFOS/PFOA	DIN 38414-14: 2011-08
	<i>Salmonella spp.</i>	BGK e.V., IV C1 (2006) (F)
	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	DIN 38411 (F)
	<i>Enterococcaceae</i>	DIN 7899-2 (F)
	<i>Clostridium perfringens</i>	ASU L 00.00-57, DIN EN ISO 7937 (F)
	Pharmaceutical residues: screening of 99 substances, quantification of Carbamazepine, Carithromycin, Ciprofloxacin, Diclofenac, Ethinylestradiol/Estradiol, Tetracyclines	HA JB 302, 2021-04; HPLC- MS/MS

- **Spanish pilot region**

Water sampling and analysis has continued being carried out by the external laboratory TecnoLab Laboratorios SL (Málaga, Spain), which oversees laboratory analyses for the majority of the parameters in reclaimed water and local well water. Continuous record of several parameters listed in 3.2 sub-chapter is also obtained by a data logger (Hach®) using submerged water probes in a reclaimed water tank (**Figure 6**).

Figure 6: Submerged probes in reclaimed water (left); data logger Hach® (right)

Mango and avocado leaves were sampled in November 2024 (M24), July 2025 (M32) and November 2025 (M36) (**Figure 7**), by selecting trees and units completely developed and with good shape, within an intermediate height of the tree, generally at the middle of the growing season or during critical stages of the phenological cycle, as flowering or fruit development. The selection of the moment and the type of leaf is crucial to obtain representative results. In the case of avocado and mango, sampling is done in autumn-winter, except for the last sampling campaign, carried out in summer.

Figure 7: Mango leaf sampling for foliar analysis in Nov. 2024 at Spanish pilot region.

Leaves were cleaned to remove surficial dirt that could affect results, and then dried under controlled temperature. Later, leaves are grinded, and several chemical analyses are made to determine nutrient concentrations. Results will be compared with optimal ranges for each parameter depending on the crop (Schaffer *et al.*, 2013), which will allow us to determine whether the nutrient concentrations are within those limits.

A mango fruit sampling campaign was carried out in September 2025 (M34). This sampling campaign (**Figure 8**) consisted in taking 49 mango fruits from the three treatments (i.e., T1 = 15 fruits, T2 = 16 fruits, T3 = 18 fruits), so fruit quality analysis could be performed. This campaign was used to analyse pharmaceutical and emerging compounds as well.

Figure 8: Mango fruit sampling for analysis in Sept. 2025 at Spanish pilot region.

Soil samples were taken directly from the portion of soil closer to each sampled tree, using hoe and spade to remove the most surficial layer (**Figure 9**). Three additional sampling campaigns have been done until now in June 2023 (M7), March 2024 (M16) and December 2024 (M25), in those trees where lysimeters are also installed. Samples were stored in 2 litres plastic bags and shipped in cooling boxes with ice packs for further analysis by Eurofins (Lleida, Spain), an external lab. Here, gravimetry is applied for analysing soil humidity and texture, potentiometry for pH and conductimetry for EC. Potentiometric titration is made for the measurement of organic carbon, organic matter, equivalent calcium carbonate and active limestone. UV-VIS spectrophotometry is used for assessing N-NO₃ and P, while ICP-OES spectrometry is used for K, Ca, Mg and Na.

Figure 9: Soil sampling in December 2024 at the Spanish pilot region.

Samples for analysis of emerging and pharmaceutical compounds were taken in water (i.e., secondary treated wastewater, reclaimed water, local well water, lysimeters in soil), mango and avocado leaves and mango fruits in August 2025 (M33) (**Figure 10**). Water samples were taken into 5 ml Falcon tubes, leaves were stored in 1 litre plastic bags, while mango fruits were directly put together with all the other samples into a freezer and sent to the GLP-Certified Laboratory for Pesticide Residue Analysis of the Jaime I University (Castellón, Spain).

Figure 10: Sampling campaign for emerging and pharmaceutical compounds in secondary treated wastewater (left), soil lysimeters (middle) and leaves (right) in M33 at the Spanish pilot region.

The following **Table 6** details the specific methods applied by the external laboratories to analyse each of the parameters referred to in the field trials.

Table 6: Methods used for lab. analyses of parameters measured in the Spanish pilot region.

Matrix	Parameter/s	Method
Water	N, Total P, Ca, Mg, K, Na, Fe, S, B, Mn, Intestinal Nematodes	SOP (Standard Operating Procedure) / External
	Turbidity	SOP-FQ-003 – Internal Method based on: UNE-EN ISO 7027-1
	pH	SOP-FQ-004 – Internal Method based on: UNE-EN ISO 10523
	Electrical conductivity, Total dissolved solids (TDS)	SOP-FQ-005 – Internal Method based on: UNE-EN ISO 27888
	Chlorides (Cl)	SOP-FQ-007
	Sulphates	SOP-FQ-009 – Internal Method based on Spanish Royal Decree 3/2023
	Bicarbonates, Carbonates	SOP-FQ-012 – Internal Method
	Nitrates	SOP-FQ-013 – Internal Method based on: SM 4500-NO3 - B
	Ammonium	SOP-FQ-016 – Internal Method based on: SM 4500-NH3 – F
	Phosphates	SOP-FQ-041 – Internal Method based on: SM 4500-P - C
	Heavy metals (As, Be, Ca, Co, Cr, Cu, Mb, Ni, Se, Va)	SOP (Standard Operating Procedure) / External
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	SOP-MB-051 – Internal Method based on: APAT CNR IRSA 7030F	

	<i>Legionella spp.</i>	SOP-MB-024 – Internal Method based on commercial kit
Soil	Humidity	C5110007 Gravimetry
	pH	C5110008 Potentiometry
	EC	C5110009 Conductimetry
	Organic carbon	C5110079 Potentiometric titration
	Organic matter	C5110079 Potentiometric titration
	Equivalent calcium carbonate	Internal method - Potentiometric valorisation
	Active limestone	Internal method – Potentiometric valorisation
	N-NO3	C5110272 UV-VIS Spectrophotometry
	P	C5110080 UV-VIS Spectrophotometry
	K, Ca, Mg, Na	C5110105 ICP-OES Spectrometry
	Ca/Mg, Mg/K, Ca/K	Calculation
	Soil texture	Internal method - Gravimetry
	Fe, Cu, Mn, Zn, Mo	Internal method – ICP-OES
Leaves	Total N	C5110096 Thermal conductivity
	P, K, Ca, Mg, Fe, Zn, Cu, Mn, B, Na, Mo	C510228 ICP-OES Spectrometry
	Cl	Internal method – Potentiometric valorisation
Fruits	Dry matter, Net weight	Internal method - Gravimetry
	Brix grades	Internal method - Refractometry
	Acidity	C5110008 Potentiometry
	Maturity index	Calculation
	Firmness	Internal method – Piercing
	Colour	Sensorial estimation
	Diameter, Longitude	Direct measurement
	Cd, Pb, Hg, Ni	ICP-MS
Pesticides		
Water Leaves Fruits	Carbamazepine, Diclofenac, Clarithromycin, Azithromycin, Sulfamethoxazole, Norfloxacin, Gabapentin, Iopromide, Atrazine, Chlorpyrifos, Metoprolol, Venlafaxine, Losartan, Ciprofloxacin, Ciprofloxacin, Tramadol, Clindamycin, Erythromycin, Lincomycin	-

5 Intermediate interpretation of results and agroecological effects

The **intermediate interpretation and assessment of the results** obtained from the three pilot regions and field trials since the first stages of the project until now (i.e., **from M4/M6 to M36**) is included in this chapter.

In order to support this assessment, the chapter includes monitoring graphs and diagrams for selected parameters analysed (or a group of them) illustrating the values obtained for the period of monitoring. Similarly to previous chapters, the graphs and results are presented per pilot region.

The interpretation of results varies between each pilot region, as there are different fertilising products and harvested crops considered that require pilot-specific techniques for the evaluation of the agroecological and environmental impact.

The complete data set covering 2.5 years (from M4/M6 to M36) for all parameters monitored in each pilot region has been collected using the “standardised data collection sheet”. The data collection sheet filled in by each pilot region has been uploaded to the P2GreenN Innovation Platform (internal repository) to keep track and demonstrate the measurements and integration of results in the data collection sheet. The data collection sheets include results of macronutrients, micronutrients, pathogens, pharmaceuticals, non-essential heavy metals in recycling fertilisers, but also fertilisers quality parameters, water quality parameters, plant quality parameters, soil quality parameters, fruit/crops quality parameter, N-leaching, P-leaching, and N₂O emissions, amongst others.

For the final version of this report (i.e., D2.6 due in M44), the data collection templates will be uploaded to the public repository of P2GreenN Innovation Platform and made publicly available. D2.6 will include a specific link to get access to the data collection templates per pilot region.

- **Swedish pilot region**

Recycling fertiliser: The **Table 7** presents the results of the fertilisers used from 2023 to 2025. In 2023, the nitrogen (N) content of the urine-derived fertiliser reached 15.1 %, representing a major milestone since farmers generally prefer a minimum of 10 % N to reduce the frequency of refilling during drilling. However, the N concentration dropped to 7.8 % in 2024. This decline was attributed to two main factors: (1) hydrolysis of urea in some batches of collected urine, which converted urea to ammonium/ammonia -forms that are more volatile and harder to retain in the final product, and (2) testing of alternative prilling methods, where the addition of various binding materials diluted the N concentration while improving prill structure and handling properties.

By 2025, optimisation of the prilling process resulted in a partial recovery of nitrogen content, reaching 8.5 % N (0.085 g N g⁻¹ TS). Most of the nitrogen was present as urea (0.142 g g⁻¹ TS), with a smaller share as ammonium (0.025 g g⁻¹ TS). Minor co-

constituents included phosphate (0.012 g g⁻¹ TS) and chloride (0.073 g g⁻¹ TS). The urea-dominant speciation is agronomically favourable for rapid plant uptake if the fertiliser is promptly incorporated into the soil; however, it also underscores the need to minimise volatilisation losses through timely incorporation or appropriate placement.

The gradual improvement from 2024 to 2025 reflects ongoing optimisation of binder selection and process parameters to reduce dilution while maintaining prill integrity. Nevertheless, some residual urea hydrolysis during collection and processing likely persisted, preventing full recovery to the 2023 N levels. Further experimentation planned for subsequent production cycles will focus on refining the prilling “recipe” to stabilise N content and achieve a consistent, farmer-acceptable fertiliser formulation.

Table 7: Analysis of the fertiliser used in the Swedish pilot region.

Parameter	2023			2024	2025			
	No fertilisation	Yara fertiliser	Urine (solid)	Urine (solid)	Urine (solid)	Urine (g/g of TS)	Urine (mg/5g)	Urine (mg/L)
N-Total (%)	-	23.6	15.1	7.8	8.5	0.085	-	-
Urea (%)	-	0	30.8	7.6	-	0.142	711.8	4745.4
Urea-N (%)	-	0	14.2	3.5	-	-	-	-
NH ₄ -N (%)	-	13.3	0.9	4.3	-	0.025	123.5	823.4
NO ₃ -N (%)	-	10.3	<0.5	<0.5	-	-	-	-
PO ₄ -P (%)	-	3.6	1.4	2.3	-	0.012	61.1	407.4
Ca (%)	-	0	1.3	1.1	-	-	-	-
Mg (%)	-	0.5	0.3	0.9	-	-	-	-
K (%)	-	4.6	6	12.5	-	-	-	-
SO ₄ (%)	-	3	2.9	1.9	-	-	-	-
Tot-C (%)	-	-	26.7	-	--	-	-	-
Org-C (%)	-	-	26.6	-	-	-	-	-
Cl ⁻	-	-	-	-	-	0.073	365.5	2437.1

Field trial: Across the 2023-2025 growing seasons, the field trials at Bro (Gotland) evaluated the agronomic performance of urine-based fertiliser compared with a conventional mineral fertiliser (Yara 24-4-5) on irrigated *Planet* barley cultivated for beer production. The urine-fertilised strip was consistently placed in the middle of the field to ensure uniform conditions and minimise edge effects.

In 2023, barley yields reached 6,516 kg ha⁻¹, representing a threefold increase relative to the previous year (pre-P2GreenN data) and 51 % higher than the 10-year regional average (3,870 kg ha⁻¹). As shown in **Figure 11**, plant growth and yield parameters (number of shoots, ears, straw strength, and protein content) under urine fertilisation were comparable to those under mineral fertiliser, indicating that urine-derived nutrients supported crop development effectively. These results demonstrated that the urine

fertiliser achieved equivalent productivity to the positive control (Yara) even in its early field application phase.

Figure 11: Results from the 2023 barley harvest in the Swedish pilot region. The relative yield is the % difference between the urine and the positive control (Yara fertiliser: 24-4-5) with the negative control (no fertiliser) as the baseline (100%).

In 2024, the average yield decreased to 3,788 kg ha⁻¹, aligning with the typical yield range for the area. This reduction was largely associated with modifications in the urine prilling process and binder testing aimed at improving product integrity, which temporarily diluted nitrogen concentration (7.8 % N, **Table 7**). Despite this, yields from urine-fertilised plots remained statistically similar to those obtained with mineral fertiliser, confirming consistent crop response across treatments.

By 2025, improvements in fertiliser formulation (8.5 % N, **Table 7**) contributed to a clear yield recovery. As shown in Table 8, the urine-fertilised barley achieved 7.13-8.19 t ha⁻¹ (15 % moisture), reflecting strong agronomic performance under irrigated conditions. Grain quality parameters, including protein (11.1-11.7 %), starch (61-62 %), and thousand-grain weight (~711 g L⁻¹), were within the optimal range for malting barley and closely matched those obtained with mineral fertiliser. Straw quality was also maintained, with high straw strength (95 %) and low breakage values, supporting overall crop resilience and harvest efficiency.

Taken together, the 2023-2025 harvest data demonstrate that urine-based fertiliser can deliver yields and grain quality comparable to conventional mineral fertilisers, maintaining both productivity and suitability for beer barley production. These findings confirm the agronomic feasibility of using recycled urine nutrients as a sustainable fertilisation strategy under practical field conditions.

Table 8: Results from the harvest sampling (2024-2025) in the Swedish pilot region.

Parameters	2024		2025	
	Straw	Grain	Straw	Grain
N-tot (g/kg)	9.6	15.4	5.0	15.9
Ca (g/kg)	4.1	0.4	3.8	0.5
K (g/kg)	3.8	4.8	6.0	3.8
Mg (g/kg)	0.8	1.1	0.6	1.0
Na (g/kg)	0.2	<0.1	0.6	<0.1
P (g/kg)	1.5	3.5	0.7	2.8
S (g/kg)	1.0	1.0	0.9	1.1
Cu (mg/kg)	3	4	2	4
Fe (mg/kg)	70	40	474	35
Mn (mg/kg)	28	11	30	12
Zn (mg/kg)	14	33	8	24
	Harvest (2024)		Harvest (2025)	
Yield (kg/ha)	4 098		8 193	
Protein (%)	12.5		11.1	
Water content (%)	15.0		14.8	

Soil: The soil analyses conducted from 2023 to 2025 in the Swedish pilot region to provide evidence that the application of urine-based fertiliser maintains comparable soil quality to that achieved using conventional mineral fertilisers. In 2023, as shown in the soil's analysis (**Table 9**), no significant differences were observed between soils treated with urine-based fertiliser and those receiving mineral fertiliser. Parameters such as total nitrogen (Tot-N), total carbon (Tot-C), organic carbon (Org-C), and key macronutrients (K, Ca, Mg, and P) were within the same range across treatments. The concentrations of ammonium (NH₄-N) and nitrate (NO₃-N) were slightly higher in the fertilised soils than in the unfertilised controls, reflecting nutrient addition from both urine and mineral sources. Electrical conductivity (EC) and pH values were also similar, indicating no salinity buildup or acidification effects from urine application. These findings suggest that, at least in the short term, the urine-based fertiliser provided nutrient conditions equivalent to the traditional fertiliser without altering the fundamental soil chemical balance.

Table 9: Results from the 2023 soil sampling in the Swedish pilot region.

Soil 2023	Initial (a)	Initial (b)	No Fert (a)	No Fert (b)	Fert (a)	Fert (b)	Dried urine (a)	Dried urine (b)	Fresh urine (a)	Fresh urine (b)
Water cont. (%)	18.8	16.2	20.9	17.0	20.5	15.2	20.7	16.5	19.8	14.6
NH ₄ -N (mg/kg)	4.6	0.5	6.4	1.7	6.4	1.4	4.2	1.1	4.3	1.0
NO ₃ -N (mg/kg)	9.6	2.0	11.8	8.1	6.6	3.2	5.6	2.7	6.6	2.6
pH-H ₂ O	6.6	8.3	6.59	8.26	6.77	8.21	6.81	8.19	6.91	8.11
EC	6.9	13.1	9.5	15.6	10.1	14.2	9.6	14.5	8.6	13.4

(mS/cm)										
Tot-C (%)	2.29	2.43	2.47	1.46	2.41	1.13	2.52	1.29	2.22	0.81
Org-C (%)	2.26	0.70	2.45	0.53	2.39	0.73	2.50	0.59	2.19	0.68
Tot-N (%)	0.22	0.06	0.24	0.06	0.24	0.06	0.24	0.06	0.22	0.07
AL-K (mg/100 g)	8.28	7.27	10.3	7.9	10.1	7.9	10.2	8.4	9.6	6.1
AL-Na (mg/100 g)	2.04	3.35	2.6	3.2	2.5	2.7	3.0	3.0	3.1	2.2
AL-Ca (mg/100 g)	272	4931	313	3344	299	1816	300	2762	291	677
AL-Mg (mg/100 g)	14.7	46.2	16.4	33.6	15.6	25.4	16.8	32.4	14.5	12.4
AL-P (mg/100 g)	2.81	0.26	3.8	0.5	4.0	0.9	3.6	0.6	3.4	2.1
Titrateable acidity (mmolc/100 g)	1.7	pH> 7.0	1.7	pH> 7.0	1.6	pH> 7.0	1.5	pH> 7.0	1.6	pH> 7.0
NH ₄ Ac-K (mg/100 g)	9.8	6.6	10.7	7.5	10.6	7.8	10.6	8.5	10.1	6.5
NH ₄ Ac-Ca (mg/100 g)	315.8	565.7	335.6	566.4	326.4	554.6	334.0	572.8	324.1	525.6
NH ₄ Ac-Mg (mg/100 g)	16.1	9.9	17.1	10.4	16.5	10.7	17.2	12.0	15.3	9.7
NH ₄ Ac-Mn (mg/100 g)	0.54	0.16	0.20	0.11	0.22	0.13	0.18	0.11	0.19	0.14
NH ₄ Ac-Na (mg/100 g)	2.5	2.1	2.6	2.3	2.6	2.3	3.1	2.3	3.1	2.1

In 2024, the pre-harvest and post-harvest sampling (**Table 10**) revealed a decline in total C and N with depth, consistent with typical mineralisation and leaching dynamics. Total C in the 0-30 cm layer decreased from 22 g kg⁻¹ to 9 g kg⁻¹ post-harvest, while N-tot dropped from 2.0 to 0.8 g kg⁻¹. Nitrate and ammonium levels were moderate (NO₃: 1.6-2.5 mg 100 g⁻¹ TS; NH₄: 0.19-0.32 mg 100 g⁻¹ TS), indicating controlled N release and uptake by the crop. The measured N-min values (71-126.5 kg ha⁻¹) suggest that the applied nutrients were effectively utilised by the barley with limited residual accumulation.

By 2025 (**Table 10**), the soil maintained balanced nutrient levels and stable organic matter content, confirming the long-term compatibility of urine-based fertilisation. Total C and N contents in the surface layer (0-30 cm) were 15 and 1.5 g kg⁻¹ pre-harvest, declining slightly to 13 and 1.3 g kg⁻¹ post-harvest, respectively, an expected seasonal variation associated with plant uptake and microbial activity. The reduction in mineral N (N-min) from 42.8 kg ha⁻¹ pre-harvest to 33.2 kg ha⁻¹ post-harvest indicates efficient nutrient uptake and minimal risk of leaching. Nitrate and ammonium concentrations also decreased (NO₃: 0.97 → 0.81 mg 100 g⁻¹ TS; NH₄: 0.10 → 0.02 mg 100 g⁻¹ TS), reflecting effective nutrient cycling.

Across all years, soil pH remained within a favourable range (5.9-7.3), and macro- and micronutrient concentrations (K, Ca, Mg, Fe, Mn, Zn) stayed within agronomic norms. Particularly in 2025, elevated plant-available K and P (K-HCl: 207–166 mg 100 g⁻¹; P-HCl: 43 mg 100 g⁻¹) suggest improved fertility without nutrient imbalances or salt accumulation.

Overall, the multi-year soil analyses demonstrate that the use of urine-based fertiliser did not adversely affect soil quality. Nutrient dynamics, organic carbon stability, and pH regulation remained comparable to those observed under mineral fertilisation. These findings confirm that urine recycling can sustain productive soil conditions while supporting nutrient circularity and reducing dependency on synthetic fertilisers in barley cultivation systems.

Table 10: Results from 2024-2025 for soil sampling in the Swedish pilot region.

Parameters	2024 a**	2024 b**	2025 a*	2025 a**
C-tot (g/kg)	22	9	15	13
N-tot (g/kg)	2.0	0.8	1.5	1.3
TS (%)	90.7	94.3	84.3	89.2
NO ₃ (mg/100gTS)	1.60	2.48	0.97	0.81
NH ₄ (mg/100gTS)	0.19	0.32	0.10	0.02
NO ₃ (kg/ha)	63.9	112.1	38.9	32.4
NH ₄ (kg/ha)	7.4	14.3	3.9	0.8
N-min (kg/ha)	71.0	126.5	42.8	33.2
pH	5.9	7.6	7.3	6.8
P (mg/100g)	7.6	4.4	6.7	6.5
K (mg/100g)	11.2	6.5	13.8	9.4
Mg (mg/100g)	11.2	10.6	12.4	5.7
Ca (mg/100g)	173	669	372	235
Na (mg/100g)	1.8	1.9	1.4	2.8
Al (mg/100g)	24	17	18	14
Fe (mg/100g)	18	17	30	27
K-HCl (mg/100g)	104	122	207	166
P-HCl (mg/100g)	4	28	43	43
Cu-HCl (mg/100g)	7.9	9.6	14.2	12.6

Legend: (a) 0-30cm; (b) 30-60cm; *pre harvest, **post-harvest.

Beer production: The barley harvested during the 2023-2025 field trials was used to evaluate the suitability of urine-based fertiliser for malting and brewing applications. The 2023 harvest (70 kg total) and the 2024 harvest (300 kg total) were shipped to the *Versuchs- und Lehranstalt für Brauerei* (VLB) in Berlin for analyses and small-scale malting, as no facilities in Sweden were available to process such small quantities.

The 2023 harvest exhibited a protein concentration exceeding 12%, rendering the batch unsuitable for standard malting due to excessive nitrogen content. This was, however, a national trend rather than an effect of the fertiliser, as heavy and prolonged rainfall across Sweden resulted in elevated grain protein and poor grain-filling across several crops, including malting barley and milling wheat. Despite the high protein levels, Gotlands Bryggeri confirmed that the barley quality was acceptable for experimental brewing. Nevertheless, 2023 marked one of the poorest Swedish harvests in the last 30 years, which contextualises the deviation in protein content.

In contrast, the 2024-2025 barley samples demonstrated clear improvements in grain composition and malting characteristics. As shown by the VLB analyses, grain nitrogen contents of 1.87% and 1.78% correspond to protein levels of 11.7% and 11.1%, respectively, well within the optimal range for malting and notably lower than those from 2023. These values align with the field observations (**Figure 11**), confirming that urine-fertilised barley achieved grain protein levels comparable to those produced with mineral fertiliser.

All key quality parameters met or exceeded standard malting specifications. Test weights were high (711 and 706 g L⁻¹), purity and grain sorting were excellent (≈99.5%), and clarity losses remained minimal (0.53-0.58%). Starch content (61.5-61.8%) and harvest moisture (14.8-15.0%) were within optimal ranges for storage and malt extract potential. Moreover, ergosterol concentrations (15.6 and 14.9 mg kg⁻¹) indicated low fungal contamination, consistent with the good straw strength (95/100) and lodging resistance observed in the field. Yield performance was equally robust, with 7.09 and 8.16 t ha⁻¹ (15% moisture) recorded in 2025, matching or exceeding the 2023 irrigated trial yields and confirming the agronomic reliability of urine, based fertilisation.

The pharmaceutical residue analysis (**Figure 12**) further confirmed the safety and integrity of the circular fertilisation process. Target compounds - lamotrigine, fexofenadine, desvenlafaxine, metoprolol, citalopram, atenolol, and carbamazepine - were detected exclusively in the dried urine fertiliser, with desvenlafaxine (≈700 ng g⁻¹) and carbamazepine (≈200 ng g⁻¹) being the most abundant. However, no pharmaceutical residues were detected in any other tested matrices, including soil, irrigation water, plant tissue, brewing water and, final beer products. Quality control recoveries were within the acceptable analytical range (60-140%), validating the robustness of the LC-MS/MS results.

Figure 12: Occurrence of pharmaceuticals in dried-urine samples.

Taken together, these findings demonstrate that urine-derived fertiliser can produce high-quality malting barley without compromising yield, grain composition, or beer safety. The absence of pharmaceutical transfer through the food chain confirms the environmental and consumer safety of this circular nutrient-recovery approach, reinforcing its feasibility as a sustainable alternative to synthetic fertilisers in beer production systems.

- **German pilot region**

Recycling fertilisers: the composition and quality of the compost fertiliser used for the greenhouse trial with kohlrabi and the field trial with rye is shown in **Table 11**. Main findings of the analyses done were that the concentrations of heavy metals, pathogens, PAHs, PFAS and DLCs were well-below the thresholds specified for compost fertilisers in Germany (according to German Fertiliser Ordinance and German Biowaste Ordinance). Another interesting finding was that the number of pathogens generally decreased during the winter storage period from M10 to M15, especially for *Clostridium perfringens*. Contrarily, the concentrations of N (1.03% in M10, 1.01% in M15) and the pharmaceutical indicator substance Doxycycline (0.011 mg/kg in M10, 0.012 mg/kg in M15) were relatively stable.

Unlike faecal compost, the Aurin[®] fertiliser contains a significant amount of N in both, ammonium and nitrate forms (**Table 11**), indicating a readily available N supply for plants. Like the compost, further essential nutrients for plant growth such as P, K, B, Fe, and Zn are provided by Aurin[®]. However, the presence of Na⁺ and Cl⁻ may require careful consideration, as they can potentially affect soil salinity and plant growth. To facilitate optimal plant growth and avoid nutrient pollution, both fertilisers (faecal compost and Aurin[®]) have been applied together in the greenhouse trial with kohlrabi and the field trials with rye, zucchini and buckwheat. Fertiliser doses were adjusted to fit plant N and P demand to avoid overfertilisation. The incorporation of compost prior to sowing/planting provides an initial supply of nutrients, while the liquid Aurin[®] fertiliser can be applied at

one or more timepoints during crop growth when plant N demand is high, thereby also counteracting salt stress.

Table 11: Composition and quality of faecal compost used for the greenhouse trial with kohlrabi and the field trial with rye, and Aurin® fertiliser in general.

The faecal compost was obtained from Finizio GmbH and analysis results for DLCs, pathogens in M10, general parameters, macro- and micronutrients, and heavy metals were provided the REGION.innovativ project zirkulierBAR funded by the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research. Analyses for pharmaceuticals, other organic pollutants, and pathogens in M15 were done within P2Green to complement the dataset. Values for Aurin® are based on VN manufacturer's specifications.

Fertilisers	Parameters	Composition	Amount	Unit
Faecal compost	DLCs: polychlorinated dibenzodioxins/furans (PCDD/PCDF) and dioxin-like polychlorinated biphenyls (dl-PCB)	Sum of PCDD/PCDF, dl-PCB	3.33	ng/kg DM
		PCDD/PCDF	2.78	ng/kg DM
		dl-PCB	0.545	ng/kg DM
	Pharmaceuticals and other organic pollutants	Total PAHs (EPA 16)	2.6	mg/kg DM
		Total PFAS	bdl	mg/kg DM
		Tetracyclines: Doxycycline	0.012	mg/kg DM
	Pathogens (M10, before winter)	<i>Clostridium perfringens</i>	> 1500	CFU/g FM
		<i>E. coli</i>	15	MPN/g FM
		<i>Enterococcus</i>	450	MPN/g FM
		<i>Salmonella spp.</i>	0	Findings in 50 g FM
	Pathogens (M15, after winter)	<i>Clostridium perfringens</i>	< 100	CFU/g FM
		<i>E. coli</i>	< 10	MPN/g FM
		<i>Enterococcus</i>	95	MPN/g FM
		<i>Salmonella spp.</i>	0	Findings in 50 g FM
	General parameters	Dry matter content	55.7	% FM
		Organic matter	21.2	% DM
		Alkaline active ingredients	6.68	% _{CaO} DM
		pH	9.1	-
		Salt content	0.23	% _{KCl} DM
		Carbon content	14	% DM
	Macronutrients	Total N	1.03	% DM
		Ammonium-N	66	mg/kg FM
		Nitrate-N	17	mg/kg FM
Plant available N		< 0.01	% FM	
Total P (P ₂ O ₅)		1.05	% DM	
Potassium oxide (K ₂ O)		1.08	% DM	

		Calcium	3.64	% DM
		Magnesium oxide (MgO)	1.02	% DM
		Sodium	0.14	% DM
		Selen	0.21	% DM
		Sulphur	0.18	% DM
	Micronutrients	Cobalt	0.0011	% DM
		Copper	0.003	% DM
		Iron	2.00	% DM
		Manganese	0.076	% DM
		Molybdenum	0.0005	% DM
		Zinc	0.014	% DM
	Heavy metals	Arsenic	7.66	mg/kg DM
		Lead	28	mg/kg DM
		Cadmium	0.23	mg/kg DM
		Chromium	77	mg/kg DM
		Nickel	40.7	mg/kg DM
		Quicksilver	0.085	mg/kg DM
Thallium		bdl	mg/kg DM	
Aurin®	Chemical composition	Total N	4.2	%
		Ammonium N	2.1	
		Nitrate N	2.1	
		Phosphate (P ₂ O ₅)	0.4	
		Potassium oxide (K ₂ O)	1.8	
		Sodium	1.7	
		Sulphur trioxide (SO ₃)	0.8	
		Chloride	3.1	
		Boron	0.0015	
		Iron	0.0001	
		Zinc	0.0012	
		Total organic carbon	0.1	

Note: bdl, below detection limit; DM, dry matter; FM, fresh matter

The results of the DIN-SPEC 91421-based analyses on the first batch of faecal compost produced by GE in M31 are shown in **Table 12**. All analysed PAHs and PFAS were below the detection limit and thus comply with the safety standards for compost from biowaste. A sample for the pharmaceutical screening and quantification of indicator substances was taken and is currently analysed. The hygiene parameters fulfilled the set threshold values for *E. coli*, *Enterococcus* and *Salmonella* spp. directly after sieving the compost in M31, indicating hygienic safety of the faecal compost. However, there were some concerns regarding the relatively high *C. perfringens* count (no threshold value defined), which led to more stringent safety measures for applying the faecal compost on the field trial site

required by the fertiliser authority of Lower Saxony. Another sample for hygiene parameters taken shortly before the field application in M32 showed again a very low *C. perfringens* count that was below detection limit (changes in hygiene parameters during the treatment process are further discussed below). The general parameters were in the expected range for a stable compost product, with the low self-heating temperature indicating a high degree of decomposition, which was also confirmed by the accredited laboratory (degree of composition can range from I-V, with V being the highest degree). The concentrations of macro and micronutrients were also in the expected range, with slightly higher total N and P contents than for the faecal compost used in 2024. The low ammonium-N and nitrate-N concentrations further indicated a high stability of the GE compost. The heavy metal contents were well below the threshold values specified in the DIN-SPEC 91421. In the case of chromium, the threshold value of 100 mg/kg DM from the German Biowaste Ordinance (BioAbfV) was used, because the analysis of Chromium (VI) as specified in the DIN-SPEC 91421 is not routinely done on compost products by external laboratories. The contamination of the GE compost with foreign materials was low and also below the threshold values from the DIN-SPEC 91421, pointing to an effective removal of foreign materials through the sieving process.

Overall, the results of the analyses done so far on faecal compost fertilisers (**Table 11**, **Table 12**) suggest that they can contribute to sustainable and environmentally friendly agricultural practices. Their high organic matter content and a suitable pH level can potentially improve soil health and nutrient retention, while the high P content ($P \geq 1\%$) is especially promising for enhancing plant growth on P-depleted soils. However, to avoid P-over fertilisation, this is limiting its maximum application rate compared to typical green waste compost ($P < 0.5\%$). The low levels of harmful pathogens like *E. coli* and *Salmonella* indicate that faecal compost poses minimal risks to plant and human health. Further analyses will be done on the subsequent GE compost batches to provide more robust evidence on the quality of faecal compost produced during P2Green. Moreover, comprehensive analyses on the Aurin[®] fertiliser produced by VN in P2Green will be used to evaluate the suitability of percolated urine from dry toilets as input material for the urine treatment process (Aurin[®] produced at the KWB pilot site in Eberswalde) compared to source-separated urine from urinals and urine-diverting flush toilets (imported Aurin[®] produced in Switzerland and France).

Table 12: Analysis of the composition and quality of the first faecal compost batch that was produced in M31 at the GE treatment facility in Ollsen.

Fertilisers	Parameters	Composition	Amount	Unit
	Pharmaceuticals and other organic pollutants	Total PAHs (EPA 16)	bdl	mg/kg DM
		Total PFAS	bdl	mg/kg DM
		Pharmaceutical	tba	mg/kg DM
	Hygiene parameters/pathogens (M31, directly after composting)	<i>Clostridium perfringens</i>	4200	CFU/g FM
		<i>E. coli</i>	70	MPN/g FM
		<i>Enterococcus</i>	700	MPN/g FM

	<i>Salmonella</i> spp.	0	Findings in 50 g FM
Hygiene parameters/pathogens (M32, shortly before field application)	Total aerobic microbial count	1,800,000	CFU/g FM
	<i>Clostridium perfringens</i>	<10 (bdl)	CFU/g FM
	<i>E. coli</i>	<10 (bdl)	MPN/g FM
	<i>Enterococcus</i>	<10 (bdl)	MPN/g FM
	<i>Salmonella</i> spp.	0	Findings in 50 g FM
General parameters	Raw density	0.66	kg/L FM
	Dry matter content	47.4	% FM
	Organic matter	25.4	% DM
	Alkaline active ingredients	<1 (bdl)	% _{CaO} DM
	pH	8.8	-
	Salt content	0.42	% _{KCl} FM
	Carbon content	29.4	% DM
	Germinable plant parts/seeds	0	plants/L
	Self-heating	24.5	°C
	Degree of decomposition	V	-
Macronutrients	Total N	1.39	% DM
	Ammonium-N	<100 (bdl)	mg/kg FM
	Nitrate-N	<100 (bdl)	mg/kg FM
	Plant available N	<0.01 (bdl)	% FM
	Total P (P ₂ O ₅)	1.37	% DM
	Potassium oxide (K ₂ O)	1.04	% DM
	Calcium	na	% DM
	Magnesium oxide (MgO)	0.71	% DM
	Sodium (Na ₂ O)	0.25	% DM
	Selen	0.24	mg/kg DM
Micronutrients	Sulphur	0.21	% DM
	Cobalt	1.9	mg/kg DM
	Copper	28	mg/kg DM
	Iron	4900	mg/kg DM
	Manganese	310	mg/kg DM
	Molybdenum	1.83	mg/kg DM
Heavy metals	Zinc	200	mg/kg DM
	Arsenic	1.46	mg/kg DM
	Lead	18	mg/kg DM
	Cadmium	0.3	mg/kg DM

		Chromium	12	mg/kg DM
		Nickel	7.5	mg/kg DM
		Quicksilver	0.04	mg/kg DM
		Thallium	0.03	mg/kg DM
	Foreign materials	Stones > 10 mm	0	% DM
		Total matter > 2 mm	0.142	% DM
		Glass	0.139	% DM
		Hard plastics	0	% DM
		Plastic foil	0.001	% DM
		Other	0.002	% DM

Note: bdl, below detection limit; DM, dry matter; FM, fresh matter; na, not analysed; tba, to be analysed

Hygiene parameters, in particular pathogen abundances, were monitored at different steps during the treatment process in order to adjust the treatment process if necessary (**Figure 13**). The total aerobic microbial count (TAMC) was used to monitor the general microbial activity during composting. High TAMC levels during the treatment process ($0.9\text{--}4 \times 10^8$ CFU/g) can be associated with the degradation of organic matter by thermophilic and mesophilic bacteria and are important for compost maturity (Mironov et al., 2021), while the lower TAMC in the final compost (1.8×10^6 CFU/g) points to a higher compost stability. The low/not-detectable abundances of *C. perfringens* and *E. coli* in the output from the hygienisation container point to an efficient inactivation of these pathogens during the first step of the GE composting process. On the contrary, the *Enterococcus* counts of 95000 MPN/g FM were above the threshold value for safe compost (1000 MPN/g FM) following the hygienisation step. Notably, *E. coli* and *Enterococcus* counts strongly increased during the second treatment step in the Earthflow container (27500 and 220000 MPN/g FM, respectively). This was likely due to the initial formulation of input materials, with the chosen amount of bentonite creating a very compact material that was less permissive for air and thus creating favourable conditions for the growth of anaerobic bacteria. Based on the results, the composting process was prolonged during M30 using an adjusted formulation with less bentonite and additional straw and shredded green waste to loosen the compost structure. Following this, a first compost batch was produced in M31 that fulfilled the safety criteria for both, *E. coli* and *Enterococcus*. However, the abundance of *C. perfringens* was increased to 4200 CFU/g FM during the composting process (no threshold value defined). This re-contamination could originate from the other input materials used (e.g. municipal green waste) or could be due to the high survivability of *C. perfringens* spores, which can also withstand temperatures of up to 115 °C (Bradshaw et al., 1997). Interestingly, the abundance of *C. perfringens* was reduced to below detection limit (<10 CFU/g) after one month of storing the produced faecal compost, similar to observed before with the faecal compost that was used for the field trial in 2024 after winter storage (**Table 11**). This suggests that ongoing microbial degradation processes in the compost can reduce pathogen loads during storage.

Figure 13: Overview of hygiene parameters monitored at different steps during the production of the first GE faecal compost batch.

The first sample was taken in M28 directly after treating the dry toilet contents in the hygienisation container (HyCo output). In M29, three samples were taken at different position inside the Earthflow container during the composting process (Pre-mature compost, average values of n = 3 samples shown). After adjustments in the composting treatment in M30, the resulting faecal compost (Compost product) was sampled directly after unloading the Earthflow container in M31 as well as after one month of storage in M32, shortly before the compost was applied on the field trial. In all samples, no *Salmonella spp.* were found.

Greenhouse trial: in a greenhouse with 9 soil plots (~14.4 m² per plot), the combination of faecal compost and Aurin® (recycling fertiliser treatment, 4 plots) was compared with full nutrient mineral fertilisers (mineral fertiliser treatment, 4 plots) using two repetitions in time from M11-M15 and M16-M18). In both treatments, fertilisation was adjusted to meet kohlrabi's N demand. Before the fertiliser treatments were started, a pre-trial cultivation with unfertilised kohlrabi and salad plants was done to balance differences in soil nutrient contents between plots. This pre-trial cultivation generally increased soil mineral nitrogen (N_{min}) to moderate levels due to mineralisation processes, while potassium (K) and phosphorus (P) levels were reduced to low levels.

In the first repetition with fertiliser treatments, kohlrabi biomass was higher with recycling fertilisers than with mineral fertiliser (**Figure 14-A**), suggesting that the recycling fertilisers promoted better growth by retaining N and making it more available, while the mineral fertiliser (Hakaphos® Grün 20-5-10(+2), COMPO EXPERT GmbH, Germany; composed of easily soluble salts) likely caused N leaching, which hindered plant growth.

In addition, nutrient leaching in the recycling fertiliser treatment was probably mitigated by the stepwise application of Aurin[®], with 1/3 applied in the beginning, 1/3 after one month and 1/3 after two months to avoid high NaCl concentrations in soil. Both, faecal compost and solid mineral fertiliser were incorporated into soil before planting kohlrabi. After fertiliser treatment, N_{min} was higher in compost-treated soil, indicating improved N content, though K and P levels were lower compared to mineral fertiliser (**Figure 14-B**), which was due to the stepwise application of Aurin[®]. As the original idea was to collect leachate from the bottom of the greenhouse plots, ample amounts of water were added to completely wet the soil during the first repetition. Hence, we conclude that the easily soluble mineral fertiliser was leached out from topsoil and thus not available for kohlrabi growth, whereas the organic matter from faecal compost retained nutrients and the stepwise Aurin[®] application reduced leaching. This issue was addressed in the second trial.

Figure 14: Box plots depicting (A) dry biomass of kohlrabi leaves, bulbs, and roots sampled during greenhouse experiment at IGZ, and (B) main nutrients (P, K, and N_{min}) analysed in soil throughout the first repetition. Treatments are represented by mineral fertiliser (white boxes) and recycling fertiliser-treated sites (grey boxes) (n=4).

In the second repetition, a slow-release mineral fertiliser (Osmocote Pro 3-4M 19-9-10+2MgO+TE, ICL Growing Solutions, The Netherlands) was used to reduce leaching in the mineral fertiliser plots. Otherwise, the treatment protocol was kept the same as during the first repetition, except for shorter timespans of 2-3 weeks between Aurin[®] application due to stronger crop growth. Kohlrabi biomass growth - encompassing leaves, bulbs, and roots - was lower in the treatment using recycling fertilisers compared to the mineral fertiliser treatment (**Figure 15-A**). However, this difference was not statistically significant, indicating that the two treatments had similar effects on biomass production for all parts of the kohlrabi plant.

Figure 15: Box plots depicting (A) the dry biomass of kohlrabi leaves, bulbs, and roots sampled during the greenhouse experiment at IGZ, and (B) the main nutrients (P, K, and Nmin) analysed in soil throughout the second repetition. Treatments are represented by mineral fertiliser (blue boxes) and recycling fertiliser-treated sites (brown boxes) (n=4).

The analysis of soil nutrients revealed no significant differences in phosphorus and potassium levels between the two treatments. However, Nmin was found to be significantly lower in soils treated with recycling fertilisers (**Figure 15-B**). Additional results were obtained from C/N analysis of plant and soil material, including the soil organic carbon content (Corg). In contrast to the slightly lower biomass yield in the second repetition, the total N content of Kohlrabi leaves and bulbs was higher in the recycling fertiliser treatment than in the mineral fertiliser treatment (**Figure 16**). Due to this, the total plant N uptake was significantly higher in kohlrabi leaves fertilised with faecal compost and Aurin[®], while the same amount of N was taken up in bulbs compared to mineral fertiliser use (**Figure 17**). This indicates a good nitrogen use efficiency from the recycling fertilisers during kohlrabi cultivation and underpins their N fertiliser value, particularly for Aurin[®]. Overall, the total plant N uptake during the second repetition (274 ± 28 kg/ha for

mineral fertiliser and 310 ± 41 kg/ha for recycling fertiliser) was higher than the applied amount of plant-available N (221 kg/ha on average). The difference could be due to the remaining N in soil from the first repetition, particularly in the deeper soil layer below 30 cm that was not analysed for determining N_{min} in soil, as the technical setup of the greenhouse (heating pipes below 30 cm depth) prevented deeper soil samplings. However, since kohlrabi has relatively shallow roots (main rooting horizon in 0 - 30 cm depth), a more likely explanation would be that N mineralization from the larger N_{org} pool took place during the cultivation period, increasing the amount of plant-available N. To determine the exact amount of N taken up from the fertiliser applied, a more sophisticated and expensive methodological approach would be necessary, e.g. using a stable isotope labelling approach to trace the N flows in the plant-soil system. The comparatively low plant N uptake during the first repetition (17 ± 5 kg/ha for mineral fertiliser and 27 ± 5 kg/ha for recycling fertiliser) was due to the slower growth of kohlrabi plants during winter, with low light intensities and cooler temperatures limiting biomass gains. Again, the lower N uptake in mineral fertiliser treatments can be explained by the form of mineral fertiliser applied in the first repetition, which was easily soluble and thus prone to leaching, what could have led to limited N availability in the topsoil.

Figure 16: Boxplots of total N content in kohlrabi leaves, bulbs and roots at harvest of the first repetition (2024-02-08), and at harvest of second repetition (2024-05-14). Treatments are represented by mineral fertiliser (blue boxes) and recycling fertiliser-treated sites (brown boxes) (n=4).

Figure 17: Boxplots of plant N uptake in kohlrabi leaves, bulbs and roots at harvest of the first repetition (2024-02-08), and at harvest of the second repetition (2024-05-14). Treatments are represented by mineral fertiliser (blue boxes) and recycling fertiliser-treated sites (brown boxes) (n=4).

Corg was not affected by the fertiliser treatment before, during and after the first repetition as well as at the end of the second repetition. This was expected, because the added amount of compost was relatively small compared to the existing soil organic matter pool and it is well-known that long-term application of organic amendments is needed to yield detectable increases of Corg (Diacono & Montemurro, 2010). Consequently, the fertiliser treatment also had no significant effect on the C/N ratio in soil. However, in stark contrast to Nmin (**Figure 15-B**), the soil organic N content (Norg) was significantly higher in the recycling fertiliser treatment compared to the mineral fertiliser treatment at the end of the second repetition (**Figure 18**). This suggests that while recycling fertilisers may not adversely affect kohlrabi biomass growth compared to mineral fertilisers, the immobilisation of N in soil organic matter could prevent N leaching and make more N available for plant growth in the following crop. Although it is not clear to which extent the re-mineralisation from Norg contributes to N leaching at later stages. Unfortunately, it was not possible to collect enough leachate from the greenhouse trial to analyse potential differences between the fertiliser treatments. This was possibly due to slow infiltration rates and blockages in the technical system of the lysimeter greenhouse at IGZ.

Overall, these results highlight that although recycling fertilisers did not produce a statistically significant reduction in kohlrabi biomass, the nutrient profile of the soil, particularly Nmin, may influence the effectiveness of recycling fertilisers in supporting plant growth. Also, pharmaceutical analysis carried out on the harvested kohlrabi (marketable bulbs) and in soil has shown that no quantifiable amounts of Doxycycline were found after the first and second application of faecal compost (concentrations < 0.001 mg/kg DM). This might be due to dilution effects in soil and limited uptake by plants but needs further investigation to account for repeated compost applications and other pharmaceutical residues. Notably, low uptake of pharmaceutical compounds has also been found in a previous study with white cabbage fertilised with faecal compost and a nitrified urine fertiliser (Häfner et al., 2023).

Figure 18: Boxplots of the soil organic nitrogen content (Norg) before the first repetition (2023-10-24), after the third fertilisation (2023-12-19), at the harvest of the first repetition (2024-02-09), and at the harvest of the second repetition (2024-05-15). Treatments are represented by mineral fertiliser (blue boxes) and recycling fertiliser-treated sites (brown boxes) (n=4).

Field trial in Ollsen: the recycling fertilisers (faecal compost and Aurin[®]) were compared in the field trial to a non-fertilised control, conventional mineral fertilisers, and certified organic fertilisers (green waste compost, vinasse and guano). The applied ratios of the different fertilisers were adjusted to provide the same amount of N and P for plant growth between the recycling fertiliser, mineral fertiliser and organic fertiliser treatments (based on rye N and P demand and taking into account the low N availability/delayed N release from compost). The field trial was performed over two different growing seasons in summer 2024 and summer 2025.

In 2024, the field trial in Ollsen was conducted with rye (*Secale cereale*), which was grown from M17 to M21. The mean dry rye ear biomass in the treatment with recycling fertilisers was higher compared to the other treatments (**Table 13**). However, this difference in

biomass among treatments was not statistically significant (**Figure 19, Table 13**). A similar pattern was observed for shoot biomass, where the recycling fertiliser treatment exhibited a higher mean biomass, though this was also not statistically significant. The only significant difference in shoot biomass was observed between the sampling timepoints. The reason for these unexpected results is likely a high spatial variability in the field, which could not be overcome with the used Latin Square design and number of replicates. This is supported by the high variation between plots, especially for the control plots with no fertilisation (**Figure 19, Table 13**).

Despite that, the treatment with recycling fertilisers not only resulted in higher mean values of essential nutrients like K, magnesium, Nmin (**Figure 20**), and P in soil, but also corresponded to an increase in dry rye ear and shoot biomass compared to the other treatments (**Table 13**). The higher Nmin availability in the recycling fertiliser treatment likely contributed to improved biomass accumulation, although there were no significant differences in shoot and ear biomass between the fertiliser treatments due to the high variability in the experimental field. The rye ears sampled from recycling fertiliser treatments showed a relatively high protein content of 10.4%, while the starch content of 42% was around 24% lower compared to the northern German average of 2024 (LUFA Nord-West 2024), possibly due to the glumes having a much lower starch content than the grains, diluting the total starch content in the rye ears.

Figure 19: Box plots of (A) Rye ears, (B) Rye shoots biomass collected in the field with untreated plots (red boxes), mineral fertilisers treated plots (green boxes), organic fertiliser treated plots (cyan boxes), and recycling fertilisers treated sites (purple boxes) ($n=4$). The lower and upper limits of the boxes represent the 25th and 75th percentiles, respectively; with the horizontal line inside the box as the median, and lower and upper whiskers show the 10th and 90th percentiles, respectively. Note that filled black circles are data falling outside the 10th and 90th percentiles. Note that the y-axis in c and d is log-scaled.

Figure 20: Box plots of Nmin analysed at three soil depths: 0 to 30 cm, 30 to 60 cm, and 60 to 90 cm.

The untreated plots are represented by red boxes, mineral fertiliser-treated plots by green boxes, organic fertiliser-treated plots by cyan boxes, and recycling fertiliser-treated sites by purple boxes (n=4). The statistical results from a linear mixed-effects model analysis are presented in **Table 13**. A linear mixed-effects model, implemented via the lme function from the nlme package (version 3.1–164) in R, was used to assess differences in rye biomass and main nutrients across treatments and timepoints. The treatments included no fertiliser, mineral fertiliser, organic fertiliser, and recycling fertiliser, with treatment and timepoint as fixed factors and replicated plots as random factors. Model residuals were evaluated using quantile-quantile plots and plots of residuals versus fitted values. Log transformation of dependent variables was applied to meet the assumptions of normality and homogeneity. For significant effects, post-hoc contrast analysis was conducted using the lsmeans function from the lsmeans package (version 3.1–164) in R.

Table 13: Linear mixed effect model results for the effect of treatment on biomass and main soil nutrients in the German pilot region.

Variables	Factors	numDF	denDF	F	P
Rye Ears (g m ⁻²)	Treatment	3	12	0.348	0.79
Shoots (g m ⁻²)	Treatment	3	12	1.991	0.169
	Timepoint	1	12	5.085	0.044
	Treatment: Timepoint	3	12	0.649	0.598
Nmin in 0-90 cm	Treatment	3	16	3.916	0.028

(kg ha ⁻¹)	Timepoint	1	128	19.646	<.0001
	Treatment: Timepoint	3	128	2.280	0.082
Phosphorus in 0-60 cm (mg 100 g ⁻¹)	Treatment	3	12	3.535	0.048
	Timepoint	1	44	9.128	0.004
	Treatment: Timepoint	3	44	0.436	0.728
Potassium in 0-60 cm (mg 100 g ⁻¹)	Treatment	3	12	1.069	0.399
	Timepoint	1	44	1.494	0.228
	Treatment: Timepoint	3	44	0.279	0.840

Note: Significant differences at $p < 0.05$ are indicated in bold letters (F-statistics, numDF: numerator degrees of freedom; denDF: denominator degrees of freedom).

Data on the effects of different fertiliser treatments (mineral, organic, recycling, or no fertiliser) on rye plant growth and soil nutrient content is presented in **(Table 14)**. By analysing the mean values and standard deviations, we can observe that mineral and organic fertilisers generally led to higher ear and shoot weights compared to the control group. However, the effects on soil nutrient content varied depending on the specific element. For example, mineral fertiliser often increased the levels of Nmin and P, while organic fertiliser had a more pronounced effect on increasing K and magnesium. Recycling fertiliser showed mixed results, sometimes outperforming mineral and organic fertilisers, and sometimes performing similarly. Some of these differences can be explained by the distinct composition of the fertilisers applied and the fact that fertiliser application rates were adjusted to meet the same N and P application rates for each treatment, while application rates for other nutrients were not adjusted for reasons of practicability. The relatively high standard deviations for many measurements indicate that other factors besides fertiliser application may also influence the outcomes.

Table 14: Mean values and standard deviations (\pm) of dry rye biomass, soil macronutrients, soil micronutrients, and soil pH measured during the field trial in the German pilot region.

Higher mean values are highlighted in bold, with an asterisk (*) indicating statistical significance. For soil parameters, mean values were calculated from samples of different soil depths (Nmin: 0-30, 30-60 and 60-90 cm; others: 0-30 and 30-60 cm).

Timepoint	Elements & units	Mean & Standard deviation			
		No fertiliser	Mineral fertiliser	Organic fertiliser	Recycling fertiliser
At harvest	Ears (dry Rye) (g m⁻²)	199.56 ± 65.20	205.32 ± 33.42	226.93 ± 24.08	230.89 ± 71.85
Before harvest	Shoots (dry Rye) (g m⁻²)	348.566 ± 105.85	428.93 ± 96.09	531.2667 ± 118.837	566.5 ± 232.16
At harvest		333.07 ± 124.198	393.87 ± 71.68	421.13 ± 45.26	490.23 ± 130.14
Before fertilisation	Copper (mg kg ⁻¹)	0.8 ± 0.424	0.62 ± 0.287	0.54 ± 0.047	0.6 ± 0.14
At harvest		0.56 ± 0.05	0.55 ± 0.05	0.57 ± 0.046	0.55 ± 0.05
Before fertilisation	Potassium (mg 100g ⁻¹)	4.4 ± 2.287	3.47 ± 2.07	4.57 \pm 2.847	5.587 \pm 3.904

At harvest		3.75 ± 0.69	3.45 ± 0.908	4.07 ± 1.138	4.25 ± 0.62
Before fertilisation	Magnesium (mg 100g ⁻¹)	1.88 ± 1.20	1.37 ± 0.55	2.35 ± 3.064	3.362 ± 3.17
At harvest		1.25 ± 0.374	1.2 ± 0.21	1.41 ± 0.556	1.6 ± 0.21
Before fertilisation	Manganese (mg kg ⁻¹)	37 ± 23.02	24 ± 7.393	31.75 ± 12.09	29.75 ± 12.84
At harvest		22.5 ± 0.53	21.125 ± 1.246	18 ± 2.13 8	21 ± 1.06
Before fertilisation	Sodium (mg kg ⁻¹)	2.75 ± 0.957	2.25 ± 0.957	2.25 ± 0.5	2.25 ± 1.25
At harvest		2 ± 0	2 ± 0	8.5 ± 4.81	6 ± 3.207
Before fertilisation	Nmin (kg ha ⁻¹)	4.66 ± 3.77	5.916 ± 5.14	6.08 ± 5.23	4.83 ± 4.569
At harvest		6.96 ± 5.10	14.269 ± 13.99	9.07 ± 6.29	15.769 ± 8.47*
Before fertilisation	Phosphorus (mg 100g ⁻¹)	6.65 ± 1.277	7.65 ± 2.625	6.275 ± 0.887	6.987 ± 0.71
At harvest		5.8 ± 0.37	6.53 ± 0.267	5.4 ± 9.5E-15	6.6 ± 0.427 *
Before fertilisation	Smin (kg ha ⁻¹)	7.75 ± 1.70	9 ± 3.65	11.75 ± 2.629	10 ± 6.055
At harvest		13 (single measurement, no replicate)	NA	29 (single measurement, no replicate)	23 (single measurement, no replicate)
Before fertilisation	Dry matter content (%)	91.08 ± 2.00	90.14 ± 3.499	90.566 ± 2.14	91.325 ± 1.80
At harvest		94.307 ± 1.98	94.38 ± 2.39	94.588 ± 2.23	94.31 ± 2.32
Before fertilisation	Zinc (mg kg ⁻¹)	1.52 ± 0.655	2.15 ± 1.047	1.05 ± 0.58	1.3 ± 0.627
At harvest		0.85 ± 0.267	1.5 ± 0.21	1.05 ± 0.16	0.85 ± 0.27
Before fertilisation	pH	4.77 ± 0.31	4.55 ± 0.177	4.66 ± 0.396	4.9 ± 0.49
At harvest		4.425 ± 0.04	4.41 ± 0.155	4.6 ± 9.5 E-16	4.5 ± 0

Also, for the field trial with rye in 2024, additional results were obtained from C/N analysis of plant and soil material. Total plant N contents were clearly increased by fertilisation, with some variations between the applied fertiliser type (**Figure 21**). During the growth phase of rye (2024-06-20), the organic fertiliser treatment led to the highest increase of shoot (i.e. total aboveground biomass) N contents, followed by the recycling fertiliser treatment. However, this effect was only significant for the organic fertiliser treatment compared to the unfertilised control. At the time of harvest (2024-08-12), the N content of rye straw and rye ears was increased in all fertiliser treatments (mineral, organic, recycling) compared to the unfertilised control. This time, the effect was only significant for the recycling fertiliser treatment, also showing the highest N contents on average. This underpins our conclusion from the greenhouse trial with kohlrabi that the used combination of faecal compost and Aurin[®] is associated with efficient N fertilisation, also for different types of crops. Nevertheless, more experiments with a larger variety of different agricultural and horticultural crops are needed to generalize this interpretation. When looking at the total plant N uptake (**Figure 22**), it becomes obvious that the effect was more pronounced on the rye straw compared to the rye ears. Again, the increase of

N uptake in rye straw was only significant for recycling fertiliser treatment. The lack of a significant increase in the rye ears might be due to the above-described sub-optimal growth conditions for rye this year, possibly reducing the amount of plant resources allocated to grain production. The total N uptake determined in straw and shoots (67 ± 16 kg/ha for mineral fertiliser, 83 ± 17 kg/ha for recycling fertiliser, 70 ± 16 kg/ha for organic fertiliser, and 50 ± 19 kg/ha for no fertiliser) also indicated a relatively low N use efficiency of the rye during the monitored growing season. Remarkably, the trend to higher N uptake in shoots of organic fertiliser and recycling fertiliser treatments during the growth phase points to a faster N uptake compared to mineral fertiliser and no fertiliser treatments.

Figure 21: Boxplots of the total N content in rye shoots during growth (2024-06-20) as well as rye straw and ears at the time of harvest (2024-08-12). Samples were collected in the field from untreated plots (red boxes), mineral fertilisers treated plots (green boxes), organic fertiliser treated plots (cyan boxes), and recycling fertilisers treated sites (purple boxes) (n=4).

Figure 22: Boxplots of plant N uptake in rye shoots during growth (2024-06-20) as well as rye straw and ears at the time of harvest (2024-08-12).

Samples were collected in the field from untreated plots (red boxes), mineral fertilisers treated plots (green boxes), organic fertiliser treated plots (cyan boxes), and recycling fertilisers treated sites (purple boxes) (n=4).

Similar to the greenhouse trial with kohlrabi, Corg in the field trial was not affected by the fertiliser treatment at the time of rye harvest. There was also no effect on the total N and Norg contents, which were similar between all treatments, including the unfertilised control. This is unsurprising, because the soil from the field trial at Vagtshoff has, on average, a five-times higher organic matter pool (Corg & Norg) compared to the greenhouse soil at IGZ. Together with the lower fertiliser application rate in the field trial (116 kg N/ha for rye in 2024), this makes it much harder to detect potential effects of compost fertiliser application on Corg and Norg. In consequence, long-term field trials are needed to determine possible positive effects of faecal compost application on soil health.

Figure 23: Photographs of the field trial with buckwheat at the time of harvest in October 2025 showing the spatial variability of plant growth in the field.

In 2025, the field trial in Ollsen was conducted with buckwheat (*Fagopyrum esculentum*), which was grown from M32 to M35. However, during the early stage of plant growth and within the main growing period in August (M33), extremely low precipitation amounts (<15 mm) and warm temperatures (up to 28 °C) led to a prolonged drought period (based on data from the two local weather stations Königsmoor and Seevetal). The missing rainfall couldn't be compensated for in September, which was also unusually dry and warm until a temperature drop occurred in the last week of September. Although there was generally more precipitation from the beginning of October, the further decreasing temperatures and frost occurring during nights inhibited further buckwheat growth and initiated plant senescence. Therefore, the plant sampling had to be conducted in mid-October (2025-10-14) before the decay of plants was too advanced. Because in some of the test plots no buckwheat was growing and there was a high heterogeneity within the field (**Figure 23**), the total aboveground biomass was sampled from all test plots. Besides buckwheat, this also included self-sown plants such as goosefoot (*Chenopodium* spp.), oil radish (*Raphanus sativus* var. *oleiformis*) and rye (*Secale cereale*). The quite unfavourable growing conditions led to a relatively low biomass growth in the field trial (**Figure 24**), with yield levels ranging between 20 and 100 dt/ha fresh mass. In comparison, the theoretical yield level for buckwheat grown for use as silage in Lower Saxony is stated with 350 dt/ha

fresh mass by the local chamber of agriculture. In general, there was also no significant difference in the biomass production between the different fertiliser treatments, because the within-field variability was much higher than the fertiliser effect (**Table 15**). Notably, there was again a tendency for the highest biomass gains in the recycling fertiliser treatment, suggesting that the combined application of faecal compost and Aurin® could have a positive effect during drought conditions compared to mineral fertilisation alone. However, further studies are needed to test this hypothesis.

Figure 24: Boxplots of plant yield (left) and total dry biomass of shoots (right) at the end of the field trial with buckwheat in 2025. Samples were collected in the field from untreated plots (red boxes), mineral fertilisers treated plots (green boxes), organic fertiliser treated plots (cyan boxes), and recycling fertilisers treated sites (purple boxes) (n=4).

Soil samples were taken prior to cultivation in spring (2025-04-17) and at the time of harvest (2025-10-14). The sampling in spring showed comparable N_{min} contents in all fertiliser treatments and soil depths (**Figure 25**). While the N_{min} in 0-30 cm soil depth, in general, was lower at the time of harvest (except for recycling fertiliser), the N_{min} in 30-60 and 60-90 cm increased for all fertiliser treatments. This suggests that N uptake took mainly place in the topsoil and that not all N applied to the topsoil before it could leach to deeper soil layers. In addition, N mineralization from soil organic matter could also take place in deeper soil layers. In contrast to what was observed before in the greenhouse trial with kohlrabi, the recycling fertiliser treatment showed a trend to (insignificantly) higher N_{min} values in all soil depths at the time of harvest. As this was a single measurement in time, it is unclear how the increased N_{min} values were related to the higher biomass found in the recycling fertiliser treatment or a possible N re-mineralisation from the faecal compost applied before. Nevertheless, it demonstrated that there is a need for monitoring or modelling the nitrate leaching potential from recycling fertiliser application to assess if there are potential trade-offs. Another unexpected result is the relatively high N_{min} value in the unfertilised control in 60-90 cm depth. This again is likely

due to ongoing N mineralisation from Norg in deeper soil and limited plant N uptake during summer, as lateral transport between fertilised and unfertilised test plots seems very unlikely based on the low precipitation amounts in summer. Regarding the other nutrients (Cu, Mg, Mn, Na, Zn), it is noticeable that in the mineral fertiliser treatment the concentrations in soil were generally depleted compared to the unfertilised control, while this was not the case for the recycling fertiliser and organic fertiliser treatments. This is likely due to the fact that the supplied mineral fertilisers focus on the main nutrients (N, P, K) and the increased plant growth from fertilisation leading to a net uptake of other nutrients. A more comprehensive monitoring of soil nutrients will be done in the following growing season in 2026.

Overall, our results highlight the potential of recycling fertilisers to improve nutrient availability but suggest that other factors, such as locally varying soil conditions, crop type, or nutrient uptake efficiency, might influence their overall effectiveness in promoting biomass growth.

Figure 25: Box plots of mineral nitrogen content (Nmin) in soil analysed at three soil depths: 0 to 30 cm, 30 to 60 cm, and 60 to 90 cm.

Samples were taken before fertilisation in spring (2025-04-17) and at the time of harvest in October (2025-10-14). The untreated plots are represented by red boxes, mineral fertiliser-treated plots by green boxes, organic fertiliser-treated plots by cyan boxes, and recycling fertiliser-treated sites by purple boxes (n=4).

Table 15: Mean values and standard deviations (\pm) of yield and dry biomass of plants; macronutrients, micronutrients, dry matter content and pH of soil measured during the field trial with buckwheat in the German pilot region in 2025.

Single values (without standard deviation) were determined from mixed samples of all four plots from each treatment.

Timepoint	Elements & units	Mean & Standard deviation			
		No fertiliser	Mineral fertiliser	Organic fertiliser	Recycling fertiliser
At harvest	Yield (dt ha ⁻¹)	35.1 \pm 6.5	49.3 \pm 31.0	54.2 \pm 32.2	63.2 \pm 33.8
At harvest	Shoots (g _{dry mass} m ⁻²)	142 \pm 38	202 \pm 86	232 \pm 124	243 \pm 105
At harvest, 0-30 cm	Copper (mg kg ⁻¹)	0.9	0.5	0.8	1.0
At harvest, 30-60 cm		0.7	0.3	1.0	0.5
At harvest, 0-30 cm	Potassium (mg 100g ⁻¹)	3.6	3.2	8.0	5.1
At harvest, 30-60 cm		4.2	2.2	5.4	2.8
At harvest, 0-30 cm	Magnesium (mg 100g ⁻¹)	1.4	1.1	4	2.2
At harvest, 30-60 cm		2.2	1.1	2.2	1.2
At harvest, 0-30 cm	Manganese (mg kg ⁻¹)	33	26	38	38
At harvest, 30-60 cm		27	16	27	21
At harvest, 0-30 cm	Sodium (mg kg ⁻¹)	3	2	9	7
At harvest, 30-60 cm		2	2	7	4
Before fertilisation, 0-90 cm	Nmin (kg ha ⁻¹)	36.5 \pm 6.0	34.9 \pm 5.0	42.9 \pm 13.3	46.1 \pm 25.5
At harvest, 0-90 cm		60.5 \pm 14.1	78.5 \pm 30.2	74.9 \pm 20.6	117.9 \pm 67.6
At harvest, 0-30 cm	Phosphorus (mg 100g ⁻¹)	5.0	5.1	6.6	6.5
At harvest, 30-60 cm		6.5	4.6	6.6	4.3
At harvest, 0-30 cm	Smin (kg ha ⁻¹)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
At harvest, 30-60 cm		n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Before fertilisation, 0-90 cm	Soil dry matter content (%)	93.8 \pm 0.6	94.0 \pm 1.6	93.9 \pm 1.2	92.6 \pm 0.3
At harvest, 0-90 cm		93.6 \pm 1.2	94.4 \pm 1.0	94.1 \pm 0.8	93.6 \pm 1.0

At harvest, 0-30 cm	Zinc (mg kg ⁻¹)	1.7	1.3	1.9	2.0
At harvest, 30-60 cm		1.2	1.0	1.5	1.0
At harvest, 0-30 cm	Soil pH	4.5	4.6	5	4.9
At harvest, 30-60 cm		4.9	4.8	4.9	4.7

Note: n.a., not analysed

GHG emission measurements: The results of GHG emission measurements from the field experiment with yellow mustard at IGZ are shown in **Figure 26** and **Figure 27**. GHG emissions were determined from four different fertiliser treatments: 1) control without fertilisation (Control), 2) liquid nitrified urine fertiliser (CROP), faecal compost amended with CROP (HIT+CROP), and 4) conventional mineral fertiliser (Mineral). Emissions from the clover-based organic fertiliser (Organic) treatment that was also established in the field experiment could not be measured due to the limited number of available gas measurement chambers (14 in total). Overall, the measured emissions were highly variable, exacerbating the interpretation of potential fertiliser treatment effects. Especially for N₂O, the within treatment variability was consistently high, while the measured fluxes were relatively low throughout the whole cultivation period – often in a range of high measurement uncertainty. In consequence, no significant effects of the fertiliser treatments on the N₂O emission could be found compared to the unfertilised control. In contrast, the CO₂ emissions from soil were clearly affected by fertilisation, with higher emissions during the warmer days in June and July. The increase of CO₂ emissions was consistent for the CROP, HIT+CROP and Mineral treatments, amounting to an increase of approximately 70% over the whole cultivation period compared to the unfertilised control. This was likely due to the 3-5times higher plant biomass in the fertilised plots, providing more carbon substrates for belowground (root and soil microbial) respiration. No significant methane (CH₄) emissions could be detected during the cultivation period, which can be attributed to the well-aerated soil conditions in the sandy soil used for this experiment. Unexpectedly, there were no visible emission peaks for N₂O emission after the incorporation of mineral fertiliser and faecal compost on 16.04.2024 as well as the nitrified urine fertiliser applications on 29.04.2024 and 28.05.2024. On the one hand, this might be due to environmental factors (soil moisture, soil porosity, temperature) creating unfavourable conditions for microbial N-transforming processes associated with N₂O emissions such as denitrification. On the other hand, the emissions were not measured continuously, and emission peaks could also have occurred outside the measurement times. Therefore, we decided to gather more data on the effects of recycling fertilisers on GHG emissions in 2025 as described above (field experiment with zucchini at IGZ).

Figure 26: Measured CO₂ and N₂O emission rates from soil during the cultivation of yellow mustard fertilised with conventional mineral fertiliser (Mineral, n = 3), nitrified urine fertiliser (CROP, n = 4) and a combination of nitrified urine fertiliser and faecal compost (HIT+CROP, n = 4) in comparison to an unfertilised control (Control, n = 3).

Figure 27: Calculated cumulative CO₂ and N₂O emissions over whole cultivation period of yellow mustard fertilised with conventional mineral fertiliser (Mineral, n = 3), nitrified urine fertiliser (CROP, n = 4) and a combination of nitrified urine fertiliser and faecal compost (HIT+CROP, n = 4) in comparison to an unfertilised control (Control, n = 3). Calculation was done by linear interpolation between measurement days and summing up the measured and interpolated daily emissions over the whole cultivation period.

- **Spanish pilot region**

Recycling fertiliser: a heatmap summarizing the values of the measured parameters in reclaimed water from M4 to M36 is depicted in **Figure 28**, offering a quick overview of the values over time. A clear influence in the high EC caused by the secondary treated effluent from the WWTP is visible until September 2023, when mixture and dilution with well water started to reduce salinity levels. Dilution with local well water reduces electrical conductivity (EC) so that crops could be irrigated with an adequate quality. This behaviour was similar in almost all macro and micronutrients, except for Boron (since April 2025). In relation to non-essential heavy metals, as mentioned in D2.5, values were relatively low, although being below thresholds in regulatory limit.

Figure 28: Heatmap of selected parameters measured in reclaimed water over time in the Spanish pilot region.

Sampled parameters and values obtained for different water sources (i.e., reclaimed water, local well water, and mixed water) is displayed in **Table 16**. This table updates values included in D2.5 and shows the first and last result for each parameter. Higher values of electrical conductivity (EC) of reclaimed water, compared with local well water, are still visible. Similar situation applies with almost every parameter. **Table 17** illustrates remarkable differences between each type of sampled water. As mentioned in D2.5, a high variability in the EC values of reclaimed water is still visible, due to problems of seawater intrusion into the sewage system that collects municipal wastewater to the WWTP.

Table 16: Sampling dates and parameters measured in the Spanish pilot region. The table shows the first and the last sample taken for the three types of sampled waters.

PARAMETER	units	FIRST SAMPLE				LAST SAMPLE			
		DATE	Reclaimed water	Well water	Mixed water	DATE	Reclaimed water	Well water	Mixed water
Electrical conductivity	µs/cm	8/3/23	5290	825	2340	10/9/25	1924	994	
						7/11/23			3290
Turbidity	UNF	8/3/23	15	0.3	8.7	10/9/25	4.8	0.68	
						7/11/23			6.8
TSS	mg/l	13/3/23	5			10/9/25	8		
Nitrogen (N)	mg/l	8/3/23	39.4	12.4	24.6	10/9/25	38.8	12.3	
						7/11/23			29.9
Nitrates (NO3-)	mg/l	15/5/23	03.01			15/9/23			52.8
		4/7/23		50.9	24.7	10/9/25	25.9	51.9	
Phosphorus (P)	mg/l	8/3/23	7.93	0.05	2.88	10/9/25	6.01	0.05	
						7/11/23			4.41
Calcium (Ca)	mg/l	13/6/23	162.4			10/9/25	77.8	83	
		11/8/23		69.5					
Magnesium (Mg)	mg/l	13/6/23	126.25			10/9/25	45.7	52.8	
		11/8/23		48.6					
Potassium (K)	mg/l	8/3/23	47.9	2.42	18.6	10/9/25	35		
						7/11/23			27.7
Sodium (Na)	mg/l	13/6/23	739.32			10/9/25	210	44	
		11/8/23		47					
Ammonium (NH4)	mg/l	8/3/23	50.68	0.4	18.5	10/9/25	42.2	0.6	
						7/11/23			30
Chloride (Cl-)	mg/l	8/3/23	1460	45.9	490	10/9/25	276	95.7	
						7/11/23			822
Sulfate (SO4 2-)	mg/l	11/8/23	184.4	73.6		10/9/25	117	104	
Bicarbonate (HCO3-)	mg/l	11/8/23	603.7	305		10/9/25	519	323	
Carbonate (CO3 2-)	mg/l	11/8/23	5	5		10/9/25	5	5	
Iron (Fe)	µg/l	11/8/23	292	19.9		10/9/25	53	50	
Sulfur (S)	mg/l	13/6/23	64			10/9/25	42	37	
		14/2/24		27.6					
Boron (B)	mg/l	13/6/23	0.53			10/9/25	0.5	0.25	
		11/8/23		0.04					
Manganese (Mn)	µg/l	13/6/23	35.1			10/9/25	27	5	
		11/8/23		2.54					
Zinc (Zn)	µg/l	16/1/24	22.7			10/9/25	23		
Arsenic (As)	µg/l	13/6/23	1.85			12/6/24	5		
Beryllium (Be)	µg/l	13/6/23	1			12/6/24	5		
Cadmium (Cd)	µg/l	13/6/23	59			12/6/24	0.5		
Cobalt (Co)	µg/l	13/6/23	1			12/6/24	5		
Chromium (Cr)	µg/l	13/6/23	1.25			12/6/24	2		
Copper (Cu)	µg/l	13/6/23	4.69			12/6/24	1.8		
Molybdenum (Mo)	µg/l	13/6/23	1.62			12/6/24	5		
Nickel (Ni)	µg/l	13/6/23	2.11			12/6/24	2		
Selenium (Se)	µg/l	13/6/23	0.49			12/6/24	10		
Vanadium (V)	µg/l	13/6/23	1.2			12/6/24	10		
DBO5	mg O2/l	13/3/23	9.9			10/9/25	10		
DQO	mg O2/l	22/5/23	58			10/9/25	<37		
E.Coli	CFU/100 ml	13/3/23	<0.1			10/9/25	30		
Nematodes	eggs/l	13/3/23	0			8/5/24	0		
Legionella	CFU/100ml	27/3/23	0			8/5/24	0		

Table 17: Mean and standard deviation of the parameters measured in the Spanish pilot region until M35.

PARAMETER	units	MEAN			S.DEVIATION		
		Reclaimed water	Well water	Mixed water	Reclaimed water	Well water	Mixed water
Electrical conductivity	µS/cm	2400,00	840.45	2219.60	1169,00	123.65	819.7
Turbidity	UNF	9,00	1.99	7.88	7.2	4.97	6.5
TSS	mg/l	13.28			12.23		
Nitrogen (N)	mg/l	32.14	12.61	25.58	17.68	3.82	7.5
Nitrates (NO3-)	mg/l	10.69	44.45	38.58	19.01	20.35	14
Phosphorus (P)	mg/l	5.24	0.21	2.29	2.74	0.55	1.4
Calcium (Ca)	mg/l	78.38	74.17		10.52	9.37	
Magnesium (Mg)	mg/l	74.51	46.88		86,00	5.74	
Potassium (K)	mg/l	32.63	3.88	0.43	19.9	4.91	0.2
Sodium (Na)	mg/l	268.84	38.15		205.19	5.6	
Ammonium (NH4)	mg/l	30.96	0.65	16.84	205.19	0.44	13.7
Chloride (Cl-)	mg/l	476.63	65.57	462.00	393.56	18.92	271.3
Sulfate (SO4 2-)	mg/l	113.64	69.88		32.02	18.92	
Bicarbonate (HCO3-)	mg/l	483.59	318.94		86,00	32,00	
Carbonate (CO3 2-)	mg/l	11.94	6.05		13.32	3.30	
Iron (Fe)	µg/l	79.04	64.69		54.97	105.13	
Sulfur (S)	mg/l	44.60	29.92		19.51	7.74	
Boron (B)	mg/l	21.45	0.15		36.89	0.1	
Manganese (Mn)	µg/l	25.68	9.34		13.46	19.18	
Zinc (Zn)	µg/l	30.46			10.66		
Arsenic (As)	µg/l	3.98			6.39		
Beryllium (Be)	µg/l	1.31			1.11		
Cadmium (Cd)	µg/l	0.10			0.14		
Cobalt (Co)	µg/l	1.31			1.11		
Chromium (Cr)	µg/l	1.56			0.60		
Copper (Cu)	µg/l	5.96			2.60		
Molybdenum (Mo)	µg/l	2.41			1.42		
Nickel (Ni)	µg/l	2.41			0.91		
Selenium (Se)	µg/l	49.27			172.11		
Vanadium (V)	µg/l	1.71			2.49		
DBO5	mg O2/l	45337.00			45541.00		
DQO	mg O2/l	100.33			124.1		
E.Coli	CFU/100 ml	157567.00			681867.9		
Nematodes	eggs/l	0.00			0.00		
Legionella	CFU/100ml	0.00			0.00		

The sodium adsorption ratio (SAR) has been updated in **Figure 29**. Values obtained depicts a low risk of having sodium-affected soils.

Figure 29: SAR time series of reclaimed and well water during the sampling period of the Spanish pilot region.

This interpretation on the EC and salinity levels was complemented considering average concentration of several ions in reclaimed and local well water (**Figure 30**). Based on this evaluation, significant differences between reclaimed water and local well water were revealed in D2.5, that are still necessary to be mentioned:

- Reclaimed water shows higher concentrations across almost all measured parameters compared to local well and mixed water.
- This disparity is particularly pronounced when looking at the macronutrients and ions concentrations, where distinct chemical profiles are discernible.
- Several ions (i.e., chloride, sodium, ammonium, total phosphorous) have higher values for reclaimed than for well water, which already highlights the potential of the reclaimed water as bio-based fertiliser.

Figure 30: Average concentration (mg/l) of several ions in reclaimed and well water.

The presence of heavy metals was analysed and monitored in reclaimed water (**Figure 31**) in order to assess the potential effect on the soil, leaves and fruits. These results were interpreted in D2.5, and the main conclusion was that despite some exceptional cases, concentrations of heavy metals in reclaimed water were below the maximum acceptable value (according to Royal Decree 1085/2024 on treated wastewater reuse) and, after one year of sampling, it was evident that heavy metal concentrations will stay below the limits in the long-run and it was agreed to stop the analyses.

Figure 31: Average concentration (µg/l) of heavy metals in reclaimed water.

High salinity levels significantly impacted the growth and yield of both crops applying T2, especially in avocado trees, as 17 trees have already died mainly affected by this issue and had to be replaced.

A time series of the monitoring of the abovementioned parameters from M4 to M36 is illustrated in **Figure 32-A**. A pronounced variability of EC of raw wastewater throughout the sampling period can be observed, as well as values generally over 2,000 µS/cm. A remarkable stabilization of EC values in reclaimed water is visible since the ending of 2023.

With regards to Cl⁻ and Na⁺ values in reclaimed water, **Figure 32-B** highlights the dependence and interrelation with the EC values shown in **Figure 32-A**. On the other hand, **Figure 32-C** shows the time series of N, P and K content in reclaimed water, which continue with similar behaviours that registered in D2.5, with values below 50 mg/l and 10 mg/l, respectively. An anomaly was detected in February 2025 regarding K, with a very high value (>120 mg/l), which is not coinciding with another variation and can be a laboratory error.

Figure 32: Time series of (A) electrical conductivity of the sampled waters; (B) Cl⁻ and Na⁺ of reclaimed water and (C) NPK of reclaimed water.

In terms of pathogens, *Escherichia coli* measured in reclaimed water (**Figure 33**) allows us to observe a lower performance of bacteria removal in Summer periods, where values are usually over 10⁴ CFU/100 ml. Nevertheless, values are generally below 1 CFU/100 ml. COD, BOD₅ and TSS follow a similar behaviour until July 2024, when COD values started to have a larger variability and maintains until today.

Figure 33: Time series of *Escherichia coli*, COD, BOD₅ and TSS measured in samples of reclaimed water from the Spanish pilot region.

Harvested crops: in order to start considering the possible effects on crops irrigated with reclaimed water, leaf samples were analysed with a focus on the nutrient content for each of the treatments applied.

A comparison of the average concentration of ions present in each treatment for the four sampling campaigns (2023-2025) is shown in **Figure 34**, as well as the optimal range for each parameter and crop (green area). It should be noticed that the values presented in the graph are indicative of natural conditions, as they reflect the optimal conditions for a particular growing season and developmental stage of the trees.

In general, nutrient values in both avocado and mango leaves are within their optimal ranges for all the sampling campaigns, excepting some parameters such as Cl⁻, Na⁺ or Fe, for all the treatments (T1: local well water and mineral fertilisation, T2: reclaimed water without fertilisation, T3: reclaimed water with adjusted fertilisation). It is important to note that during these samplings, T3 trees had not received any fertilisation yet and were irrigated with only well water.

Figure 34: Average concentration (mg/l) of nutrients in leaf analyses between 2023 and 2025 for avocado (a) and mango (b) crops. Green highlighted areas correspond to optimal ranges for the 2023 sampling period of the year.

A differentiated analysis of the macronutrients in leaves of avocado crops for the four campaigns (**Figure 35**) allows to observe very similar behaviours, with Ca, K and N within their optimal range, excepting N for T2. On the other hand, P and Mg are over their optimal range for all years and all three treatments, which can indicate an excess of the provided nutrient or a deficit in the nutrient absorption capacity of the trees.

AVOCADO - All Years Comparison

Figure 35: Macronutrients values (mg/l) from foliar analysis of avocado crops in December 2023, June 2024 (2024a) (excluding replaced trees), November 2024 (2024b) and July 2025. Green highlighted areas correspond to optimal ranges for the 2023 sampling period of the year.

For the foliar analysis carried out in mango crops (**Figure 36**), only N and P are over the optimal ranges for all treatments, while Ca⁺ and K⁺ are below their optimal ranges for T2 and T1, respectively.

MANGO - All Years Comparison

Figure 36: Macronutrients values (mg/l) from foliar analysis of mango crops in December 2023, June 2024 (2024a), November 2024 (2024b) and July 2025. Green highlighted areas correspond to optimal ranges for the 2023 sampling period of the year.

N is clearly above the recommended limits for mango crops and slightly over the limits for the avocado crops. This also occurs with Mg for avocado. Crops irrigated under T2 present higher Cl^- and Na^+ than with the other treatments, highlighting the higher concentration of these ions in reclaimed water.

For the 2023 sampling, given the brief duration of the project at that stage, significant differences in leaf nutrient concentrations were not anticipated; as the fertilisation program for T1 was not fully implemented and trees did not have substantial requirements for certain nutrients.

As indicated in D2.5, the irrigation with reclaimed water in T2 caused an excess of sodium and chlorine in the leaves of both crops, but avocado appears to more easily uptake these elements and it shows higher concentrations in the leaves.

For the June 2024 sampling, the difference in chlorine and sodium in T2 became evident, despite the decrease in EC values in reclaimed water after 2023 summer. Furthermore, some nutrients deficiencies in T2 and T3 are beginning to manifest due to the lack of mineral fertilisation. These deficiencies are more pronounced in avocado, which has higher nutritional requirements, particularly in the case of nitrogen, calcium and boron. November 2024 and July 2025 sampling campaigns also permit to distinguish lower levels of chlorine in leaves in T2 treatment. Sodium concentrations were higher in the November 2024 sampling, but the lowest values of all the monitoring were detected in July 2025.

Despite these limitations, we can still affirm that the EC problem persists when irrigating avocado crops, mainly. Even when reclaimed water is mixed with well water, the EC values remain close to 2,000 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$. Additionally to leaf sampling, a first sampling campaign of mango fruits was able to be carried out in September 2025 (M34) in the three treatments. The analyses carried out (**Table 18**) show that fruit quality parameters present values ranging within the normal thresholds in all three treatments, as indicated by the TROPS technicians, as well as good taste and texture.

Table 18: Parameters measured in harvested mango fruits in M34 (September 2025) in the Spanish pilot site

Parameter	T1	T2	T3	Units
Dry matter	18	21.7	21.7	%
Net weight	552	356	520	g
Brix grades	10.5	12.9	14.5	°Brix
Acidity (g Citric acid/100 g)	0.4	0.39	0.38	%
Maturity index	26.2	33.1	38.2	
Firmness	2	1.2	2	kgf/cm ²
Colour	Orange yellow	Orange yellow	Orange yellow	
Diameter	9.52	6.17	9.24	cm
Longitude	14.95	12.98	15.35	cm
Cd	<0.005	<0.005	<0.005	mg/kg
Pb	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	mg/kg
Hg	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	mg/kg
Ni	<0.10	<0.10	<0.10	mg/kg

Soil: as illustrated in **Figure 37**, samples of soil were taken in those points where lysimeters are also installed, so the representativeness when analysing the overall sampling can be improved. Every irrigation line has been sampled, from line 1 to line 6, and lines 1 and 5 of both crops have been sampled in two different points.

As mentioned before, soil texture has been analysed for these samples so the soil most basic properties can be known. In this way, most of the samples present a sandy loam profile (**Figure 38**), whereas only two points from the eastern part of the mango crops (M5-46 and M6-53) have a loamy profile. In general, this means that these soils have a major proportion of sand than silt or clay, that can be interpreted as soils with a nice permeability and capability of absorbing water, but also retaining it relatively enough for crops water maintenance during short amounts of time.

Figure 37: Sampling points for soil in the Spanish pilot region.

Figure 38: Ternary diagram of soil texture of the samples taken in June 2023 in the Spanish pilot region (A = avocado; M = mango).

Results of the three sampling campaigns were displayed in maps for a better understanding and comprehension (**Figure 39**, **Figure 40**, and **Figure 41**). Soil samples taken in June 2023 and March 2024 (**Figure 39** and **Figure 40**), allow to see some noticeable differences in the soil properties throughout the test site and differentiate two groups of parameters with significant similarities in their spatial distribution and variability:

- Group 1: pH, EC, N-NO₃, Ca, Mg, Na, Ca/Mg, Fe, Cu
- Group 2: Organic carbon, organic matter, P, K, Ca/K, Mg/K, Mn, Zn

Sampling carried out in December 2024 (**Figure 28**) show similar patterns in almost all analysed parameters. Nevertheless, it is important to remark higher values of electrical conductivity, mainly due to a remarkable increment of Mg, Na and K, but also Mn.

The soil analyses results have permitted to obtain an overview of the state of soil. However, more sampling campaigns under smart fertigation conditions are needed to start making conclusions about the spatial-temporal distribution of the parameters.

Figure 39: Soil sampling carried out in June 2023 and concentration of parameters in the Spanish pilot region.

Figure 40: Soil sampling carried out in March 2024 and concentration of parameters in the Spanish pilot region.

Figure 41: Soil sampling carried out in December 2024 and concentration of parameters in the Spanish pilot region.

Samples taken in M33 to analyse emerging and pharmaceutical compounds have not been analysed yet in the laboratory, due to an overload of work. Results will be available after M36.

6 Risk assessment and sampling optimisation

In this chapter, each pilot region has elaborated a **risk assessment and sampling optimisation analysis**. This internal assessment at pilot region level considers the variability in the measured parameters (based on data collected from M4/M6 to M36) and the regulatory requirements and limit references (e.g., frequency of sampling) per pilot region.

This assessment describes key parameters where low variability has been observed during the sampling campaigns - highlighting which parameters show consistency over time. On the other hand, high-risk parameters (if any) are identified and those showings occasional spikes, unexpected results, or regulatory non-compliance risk are pointed out.

This analysis concludes with proposals for reduced sampling and monitoring for low-risk parameters or suggestions for more frequent monitoring for high-risk or highly variable parameters.

- **Swedish pilot region**

Granurin (i.e., urine fertiliser developed by S360) is produced by chemically stabilising source-separated urine using a combination of pH regulating chemicals that prevent urea degradation and nitrogen losses. The stabilised urine is then dehydrated in low-energy, decentralised evaporators, concentrating the nutrients into a safe, nutrient-rich fertiliser that can be used as a liquid or further dried and granulated. The process operates at >60 °C for a minimum of two days with a maximum particle size of 40 mm, ensuring complete full pathogen inactivation.

The process described above enables several safety mechanisms to ensure a safe fertiliser. This multi-barrier sanitation chain includes:

1. Source separation (urine diversion at origin) prevents faecal contamination.
2. Chemical stabilisation (pH < 3.0 or pH >10).
3. Thermal drying (40–70 °C).
4. Low water activity (< 0.7), which halts pathogen viability.

These combined barriers ensure complete elimination of bacterial, viral, and parasitic pathogens, meeting and exceeding EU FPR hygiene and safety thresholds (Senecal et al., 2018; Senecal et al., 2020).

Regulatory requirements for urine-based fertilisers in Sweden

The certifications currently available on the market for recycled nutrients are Revaq¹, Biofertiliser², Compost³ and SPCR 178 (P-labelling of source-sorted sewage fractions).

None of the major certification rules have been able to be used for urine: Revaq has a raw material that is not source-sorted, Biofertiliser clearly states that toilet water may not be used and compost is primarily a soil improver or growing medium. The regulation concerning source-sorted fractions (SPCR 178) has been decided to be discontinued. 2024, as there have been too few users so far. In addition, none of the current regulations ensure product quality in terms of nutritional content, but current regulations are focused on ensuring that the level of contaminants is low.

There is therefore no functioning regulatory framework for source-sorted recycled nutrient fractions. However together with The Research Institutes of Sweden (RISE), Sanitation360 evaluated the risk of the fertiliser in comparison of the End-of-Waste criteria as the EU has established CE rules for recycled plant nutrition products (**Figure 42**).

Figure 42: Quality assurance of recycled plant nutrient products is based on the Swedish Environmental Code and EU regulations, but also uses other countries' national criteria and End-of-Waste criteria (if available).

By being able to recycle plant nutrients, the ambition is to increase robustness and to contribute to increased production of domestic fertiliser products in Sweden. Both the Swedish Board of Agriculture (Ekman, *et al*, 2023) and the Government Offices (Regeringskansliet, 2024) have stated that there are no criteria in the legislation that regulate when waste ceases to be waste. The regulations for recycled nutrients (New

¹ Slamanvändning och Revaq", Svenskt Vatten. Åtkomstdatum: 23 oktober 2024. [Online]. Tillgänglig vid: <https://www.svensktvatten.se/vara-sakomraden/avlopp-och-miljo/slamanvandning-och-revaq/>

² Avfall Sverige, "SPCR 120 - Biogödsel". Åtkomstdatum: 23 oktober 2024. [Online]. Tillgänglig vid: <https://www.biogodsel.se/certifiering/spcr-120/>

³ Avfall Sverige, "Certifieringsregler för kompost SPCR 152", Avfall Sverige. Åtkomstdatum: 23 oktober 2024. [Online]. Tillgänglig vid: <https://www.avfallsverige.se/fakta-statistik/certifierad-atervinning/certifieringsregler-for-kompost/>

SPCR178) contain criteria that could be used to demonstrate that the basic criteria of the Environmental Code are met (**Figure 43**).

Figure 43: Assessment according to Swedish Environmental Code means that the fertiliser product needs to be ensured that the waste can be exempted from 2020:612.

Based on the assessment by RISE, Granurin has an area of use, the nutrient content of dried urine pellet can be classified as a fertiliser product according to the regulations NEW SPCR 178, where the nutrient content requirements are based on the Fertilizer Ordinance (European Union, 2019). The fertiliser product can be classified as Product Function Category 1.CI a ii: COMPOUND SOLID INORGANIC MACRONUTRIENT FERTILIZER (**Figure 44**).

Figure 44: Simplified process diagram of different steps involved in production of urine pellets to indicate when the urine stops being waste and is considered a product.

For Granurin to be released freely on the national market, the requirement in the Regulations for Recycled Nutrients (proposed New SPCR178) is to apply the strictest application of limit values, guideline values and own requirements. The EU Regulation (2022/1009) states that nations can have higher national requirements for a CE product,

but that it is also possible to accept lower requirements for local use. This means that the requirements in the CE Regulation (2019/1009) should not actually be used as a norm for local use (European Union, 2019).

The transport of unconcentrated (fresh) urine is categorized as none-hazardous waste, and the concentrated urine as fertiliser. **Table 19** shows the classifications based on the concentrated urine.

The urine concentrate and stabilizing acids are handled with protective gloves and safety glasses and eyewash is available on site at the facility.

In terms of transportation safety, the compositional analysis shows that the urine-based fertiliser contains only low concentrations of substances with Classification, Labelling and Packaging (CLP) hazard classifications, and all are present well below thresholds that would trigger product-level classification (**Table 19**). Ammonium nitrate (<5%) and urea-nitrate (<1%) are both oxidising/combustible materials, but their very low concentrations limit any reactivity risk; their associated H-statements (H272 and H228) therefore do not influence the overall mixture classification. Both compounds also carry H319 (causes serious eye irritation), but again at levels too low to affect the fertiliser's classification. Potassium metal (<10%) is the component with the strongest hazard profile (H260, H314), but as a trace nutrient it is present in oxidised or bound form, not as reactive elemental potassium; thus, the listed hazards do not apply to the mixture in practice. All other components (urea, phosphate, magnesium, sulphate, and calcium) are unclassified and pose no chemical hazards at their reported concentrations. With water comprising up to 50% of the mixture, the product is overall non-hazardous according to CLP and does not meet criteria for ADR transport classification.

Table 19: Composition of main substances in the urine-based fertiliser product, including their concentrations and CLP hazard classifications (H-statements).

Substance Name	CAS Number	Content (%)	Hazard Statement
Ammonium-nitrate	6484-52-2	<5%	H272, H319
Urea	57-13-6	< 30%	Not Classified
Urea-nitrate	124-47-0	<1%	H228, H319
Orthophosphate as phosphorus	7723-14-0	<5%	Not Classified
Potassium	7440-09-7	<10%	H260, H314
Magnesium	7439-95-4	<2%	Not Classified
Sulphate	14808-79-8	<3%	Not Classified
Calcium	7440-70-2	<2%	Not Classified
Water		<50%	

Heavy Metals in Granurine

There are few laws in national legislation that cover content in products. National law states that fertilisers may not contain a higher content than 100 g Cd/1 ton of phosphorus (Sverigeas rikstad, 1998), as well as requirements for maximum input of metals for

spreading sewage sludge (Statens naturvårdsverksf, 1994). The EU regulation for fertiliser products (EU 2019/1009) contains requirements for maximum permitted metal content.

The levels of metals in dried urine pellets are below the criteria set out in Regulation EU 2019/1009 (Svensk Vatten, n.d.) (see **Table 20**). The content of metals meets the requirements for the maximum permitted level of cadmium (cadmium/phosphorus ratio in dried urine pellets 11.6 g Cd/kg P and maximum permitted level 100 g Cd/kg P). No metals limit the rate at full phosphorus rate, and the level of metals is below the maximum permitted level for the current product function category (PFC).

Control has also been carried out against SNFS 1994:2 and it is the amount of phosphorus that limits the dose, not metals.

Table 20: The content of heavy metals is below the maximum permitted content according to EU 2019/1009.

	Urine pellets	Limit	Urine pellets	Limit
Parameter	mg/kg DM	PFC 1.C.1 maximum permitted content mg/kg TS ⁴	g/ha at full phosphorus dose	at full at phosphorus giving g/ha ⁵
CD	0.218	1.5	0.26	0.75
Cr	6.29	300	7	40
Cu	56.6	600	66	300
HG	<0.2	1	0.2	1.5
You	13.2	70	15	25
Pb	19.8	100	23	25
Zn	235	1500	280	600

Pathogens

The requirement that products should not spread infection is found in national regulations such as Revaq⁶ and Biofertiliser⁷ but also in the Fertilizer Ordinance⁸. Regardless of the regulations, the same concentration limits apply (**Table 21**).

⁴ "Regulation - 2019/1009 - EN - EUR-Lex". Access date: 17 May 2024. [Online]. Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2019/1009/oj/swe>

⁵ Swedish Environmental Protection Agency's announcement with regulations on the protection of the environment, especially the soil, when sewage sludge is used in agriculture (SNFS 1994:2)

⁶ "Slamanvändning och Revaq", Svensk Vatten. Åtkomstdatum: 23 oktober 2024. [Online]. Tillgänglig vid: <https://www.svenskvatten.se/vara-sakomraden/avlopp-och-miljo/slamanvandning-och-revaq>

⁷ Avfall Sverige, "SPCR 120 - Biogödsel". Åtkomstdatum: 23 oktober 2024. [Online]. Tillgänglig vid: <https://www.biogodsel.se/certifiering/spcr-120/>

⁸ "Förordning - 2019/1009 - EN - EUR-Lex". Åtkomstdatum: 17 maj 2024. [Online]. Tillgänglig vid: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2019/1009/oj/swe>

Table 21: Limit of concentration for pathogens for Granurin treated at 42 °C

Pathogen	Granurin	Limit
<i>Salmonella spp.</i>	Not detected	No findings in 25 g or 25 ml
<i>Escherichia coli</i> and <i>Enterococcaceae</i> <i>Enterococcaceae</i> is optional for analysis.	Not detected	1,000 cfu per 1 g or 1 ml
<i>Ascaris suum</i> eggs	Not detected	No limit
Virus MsS2 and φX174	Not detected	No limit

Other chemical contaminants and chemical hazards

Management of visible contaminants and drug residues are two other relevant risks to manage. This is based on the possibility that the collected urine may be contaminated by missorted material that needs to be removed and that people use drugs that are excreted in urine and faeces.

The fact that PAH and PFAS do not need to be handled is based on the fact that neither PAH nor PFAS are something that is actively added to food. PAH is created when heating and burning materials, which is not a treatment method for urine pellets. PFAS are found in surface treatment products and these should not be present in the process.

Risks of visible impurities are managed by filtering incoming urine. Dried urine is processed and pelletized. Dried urine pellets undergo a visual inspection during packaging which is used to ensure that no visible foreign materials are present in the final urine-based fertiliser (European Commission, 2011).

Medical residues - background for guideline value and selected parameters

There are currently no requirements for concentrations for medical residues in products. However, the basic requirement of the Environmental Code is that products must not pose a risk to human, animal or plant health, safety or the environment.

The European Medicines Agency (EMA) has issued guidelines for the environmental risk/impact assessment (ERA or EIA) of veterinary medicinal products (VMPs). The ERA is divided into two phases, which are described in two separate guidelines. Environmental risk assessment (EMA, n.d.) does not need to proceed beyond Phase II.

- If the predicted/recalculated environmental concentration in soil (PEC_{soil}) is below the threshold value of 100 µg/kg.
- If the predicted/recalculated environmental introduction concentration from aquaculture facilities (EIA_{aquatic}) is below the threshold value of 1 µg/L.

Phase II involves more extensive testing and is based on joint EIA testing of VMP between the EU, Japan, the USA, Canada and Australia/New Zealand.

EFSA guidance documents provide guidance on the exposure assessment of soil organisms to plant protection products (PPPs) and their transformation products in accordance with Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009 of the European Parliament and of the Council. Guidance is provided for all types of concentrations potentially needed to assess ecotoxicological effects, i.e. the concentration in total soil and the concentration in pore water, both averaged over different depths and time windows.

- **German pilot region**

In the German pilot region, two different fertilisers are produced from source-separated human excreta (urine and faeces).

Aurin[®] is mainly produced from urine that percolated through dry toilet contents (“percurine”) via a three-step process:

1. Nitrification in a biological reactor to stabilise N
2. Activated-carbon filtration to remove pollutants
3. Volume reduction by evaporation in a distiller

Faecal compost is produced from dry toilet contents and several additives, also using a three-step process:

1. Hygienisation of dry toilet contents together with straw in a sanitization container (aerobic, temperatures > 65 °C for at least 7 days)
2. Composting of the hygienised material together with green waste, biochar and bentonite/clay minerals in the Earthflow container (aerobic, temperatures between 40-60 °C, 6-8 weeks)
3. Sieving of the final compost product using a 2 cm mesh to remove foreign materials

Regulatory requirements for applying human-excreta derived fertilisers in Germany:

Currently, the reuse of source separated human excreta for fertiliser production is not covered by the German national framework. The permitted raw materials for fertilisers are listed in Annexes 1 and 2 of the German Fertiliser Ordinance (Düngemittelverordnung, DüMV) and do not explicitly include human excreta. However, DüMV §4 (4) allows the usage of non-listed substances for research and experimental purposes, provided that there is no risk of harm to human or animal health or danger to the natural environment. This is being utilised for conducting the field trial in the German pilot region, where Aurin[®] and faecal compost are applied to grow rye and buckwheat. For Aurin[®] that is already authorised and produced in France, import and use would in principle also be possible through the mutual recognition of goods within the EU (Regulation (EU) 2019/515). To ensure that there is no risk of harm, recycling fertilisers are only applied if they meet the safety criteria specified in the technical rule DIN SPEC 91421:2020-12 “Quality assurance of recycling products from dry toilets for use in horticulture” (DIN, 2020). The DIN SPEC 91421 was created based on the risk assessment by Krause et al. (2020). It contains a

list of relevant monitoring parameters and methods, which particularly addresses faecal compost fertilisers, but also includes some advice for (reduced) monitoring on urine-derived fertilisers. For pollutants, threshold values (see **Table 22**) are given based on DüMV and other national and EU regulations for comparable raw materials (e.g. biowaste, animal by-products). Based on the risk assessment, additional parameters such as pharmaceutical indicator substances were included as well, although there are no existing threshold values from existing regulations.

Table 22: List of pollutants and their thresholds (labelling threshold and limit value) specified in the DIN-SPEC 91421 technical rule for faecal compost fertiliser.

Pollutant group	Analytical parameter	Labelling threshold	Limit value	Source
Foreign matter	Stones > 10 mm	n.a.	5 % DM	DüMV:2012, § 3 (1) 4
	Recycled paper, cardboard, glass, metal, plastically non-deformable plastics > 1 mm	n.a.	0,4 % DM	DüMV:2012, § 3 (1) 4
	Other plastics > 1 mm	n.a.	0,1 % DM	DüMV:2012, § 3 (1) 4
Heavy metals	Arsenic (As)	20 mg/kg DM	40 mg/kg DM	DüMV:2012, Annex 2, no. 1.4.1
	Lead (Pb)	100 mg/kg DM	150 mg/kg DM	DüMV:2012, Annex 2, no. 1.4.2
	Cadmium (Cd)	1 mg/kg DM	1.5 mg/kg DM	DüMV:2012, Annex 2, no. 1.4.3
	Chromium (Cr) (total)	300 mg/kg DM	n.a.	DüMV:2012, Annex 2, no. 1.4.4
	Chromium (Cr) (VI)	1.2 mg/kg DM	2 mg/kg DM	DüMV:2012, Annex 2, no. 1.4.5
	Copper (Cu)	200 mg/kg DM	900 mg/kg DM	DüMV:2012, Annex 1, no. 4.1.1, column 6
	Nickel (Ni)	40 mg/kg DM	80 mg/kg DM	DüMV:2012, Annex 2, no. 1.4.6
	Mercury (Hg)	0.5 mg/kg DM	1 mg/kg DM	DüMV:2012, Annex 2, no. 1.4.7
	Thallium (Tl)	0.5 mg/kg DM	1 mg/kg DM	DüMV:2012, Annex 2, no. 1.4.8
Organic pollutants	Zinc (Zn)	200 mg/kg DM	5000 mg/kg DM	DüMV:2012, Annex 1, no. 4.1.1, column 6
	PFT (Perfluorinated tensides)	0.05 mg/kg DM	0.1 mg/kg DM	DüMV:2012, Annex 2, no. 1.4.9
	Dioxin and dl-PCBh (WHO TEQ 2005)	n.a.	30 ng/kg DM	DüMV:2012, Annex 2, no. 1.4.10
Pharmaceutical residues	PAH-16	n.a.	6 mg/kg DM	REGULATION (EU) 2019/1009, Part II, CMC 3: compost, 1 e) ii
	Ciprofloxacin	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
	Clarithromycin	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
	Carbamazepine	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
	Diclofenac	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Pharmaceutical residues	Ethinyl estradiol or estradiol	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.

Epidemiologically hygienic parameters	Salmonella	n.a.	0 findings/50 g	DüMV:2012, § 5 (2) 1
	E. coli	n.a.	1 000 CFU/1g	EC 142/2011 Annex V Chap. III para. 3 no. 1a
	Enterococci	n.a.	1 000 CFU/1g	EC 142/2011 Annex V Chap. III para. 3 no. 1a
	Clostridium perfringens and spores	n.a.	0 findings/1 g	EC 142/2011 Annex IV Chap. III G no. 1 c i
	Somatic coliphages	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Phyto-hygienic parameters	Germinable seeds and parts of plants capable of sprouting	n.a.	2 plants/1 l	BioAbfV, Annex 2, 4.3.2

A comprehensive dataset on the DIN-SPEC 91421- based monitoring of faecal compost was gathered within the REGION.innovativ project zirkulierBAR (funded by the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research). The dataset has been published open access (Mühlenberg et al., 2025) and comprises the analysis results from 17 faecal compost batches produced by Finizio GmbH, including the batch “MK7” that was also used for the P2Green trials in 2024. The dataset together with the results from the first faecal compost batch produced by GE in P2Green (cf. **chapter 5, pg. 35**) will provide the basis for assessing the risks posed by different pollutants in the following parts.

Foreign matter

Aurin®: There seems to be no particular risk for foreign matter contamination from source-separated urine or percurine.

Faecal compost: Non-biodegradable materials can enter the system by inappropriate usage of dry toilets, i.e. disposal of trash or the use of wet wipes that are based on polyester fabrics. The latter are the most abundant fraction of foreign matter found in faecal compost from dry toilet contents (Krause et al., 2021). This particularly poses a risk for contributing to microplastics pollution. However, results from the first GE compost batch show that foreign matter contents are well-below the limit values, with hardly detectable plastics. This indicates that the screening step used during the treatment is suitable to remove most foreign matter from faecal compost. In conclusion, there seems no particular risk for faecal compost, although this is only based on one observation. Therefore, further monitoring is recommendable and will be done during the remaining time of P2Green. In the longer term, a similar monitoring scheme as for established biowaste composting might be used, e.g. the RAL quality assurance for compost (RAL-GZ 251) from Bundesgütegemeinschaft Kompost e. V. (BGK).

Heavy metals

Aurin®: Heavy metal concentrations have been found to be very low in concentrated urine from the treatment system (Fumasoli et al., 2016) and do not pose a particular risk for

Aurin®. However, analyses should be done to comply with the requirements from the German Fertiliser Ordinance in consultation with local authorities.

Faecal compost: In the 18 considered faecal compost batches, heavy metal concentrations were consistently below limit values. However, in some cases they reached the labelling threshold (particularly for Ni) and were close to the limit value. Heavy metals are mainly excreted via faeces (Jönsson & Vinnerås, 2013) but can also enter the system through additives (green waste, biochar, bentonite) at the composting step. Hence regular monitoring is advisable, especially if the additives are not analysed for heavy metals. A possible monitoring scheme could include batch-wise analyses at the beginning of treatment operation and on-demand analyses at a later stage, e.g. when changes in input materials occur.

Pathogens

Aurin®: Pathogens can occur in source-separated urine and especially percurine through cross-contamination from faeces. During the zirkulierBAR project, the fractions percurine, nitrified and filtered percurine, and Aurin® were analysed for hygiene parameters at six different sampling times (Krause et al., 2025). The results show that *Enterococci* occurred in the percurine and were reduced below detection limit, already after the nitrification and filtration steps. *E. coli* and *Salmonella* were not detected in all fractions. Furthermore, the evaporation step ($T > 85$ °C for multiple hours) at the end of the treatment ensures efficient elimination of pathogens. Therefore, the risk from applying Aurin® fertiliser is perceived as minimal in terms of pathogens. To substantiate this assessment, further analyses will be performed within the remaining time of P2Green. Nevertheless, care should be taken during the handling of percurine to avoid potential infections by implementing work safety measures (e.g. provision of protective equipment and hygiene guidelines to workers).

Faecal compost: Pathogens clearly pose a risk during the collection of dry toilet contents, the treatment process, and the field application of faecal compost. This not only concerns the safety of crops produced with faecal compost, also the work safety during the handling of input materials and faecal compost is a key aspect. Pathogens were repeatedly mentioned as a main concern during our exchange with national and local authorities. Thus, we put a particular emphasis on the analysis of hygiene parameters during the production of the first GE compost batch. The hygienisation step apparently worked well for inactivating *Salmonella*, *E. coli*, and *Clostridium perfringens*, since all three indicator pathogens were not detectable in the output of the sanitization container. Only *Enterococci* were found and exceeded the limit value. However, these pathogens were reduced below the threshold during the composting process. Similar observations have been made in the zirkulierBAR project before (Krause et al., 2025). Overall, the epidemic hygiene parameters showed a high variability between different faecal compost batches, with some exceeding the limit values for *Enterococci* (3 out of 17 cases) and *E. coli* (1 out of 17 cases) in the final product (Mühlenberg et al., 2025). This indicates that regular monitoring and adjustment of the composting process is necessary to ensure

hygienic safety of the faecal compost product. Consequently, based on current knowledge, it is essential to analyse the epidemic hygiene parameters for each batch produced. If the limit values are exceeded for *Salmonella*, *E. coli*, or *Enterococci*, the batch either needs to be safely disposed or re-treated to reduce these pathogens to a safe level. For *Clostridium perfringens*, the situation proved to be more complicated, as the limit value from DIN-SPEC 91421 (0 findings/1g) is almost impossible to reach in compost. The limit value was inherited from the EU Animal By-Product Regulation (EU) 142/2011 and doesn't seem to be applicable for faecal compost, which was also underlined by the exchange of knowledge with international researchers and German authorities. There are two main issues that can be related to the re-emerging of *Clostridium perfringens* during the composting process:

1. *Clostridium perfringens* is a ubiquitously occurring, strictly anaerobic, spore-forming bacterium that can survive under aerobic conditions. Thus, even if it is efficiently reduced after the hygienisation step, it can be re-introduced from other additives during the composting step such as green waste.
2. *Clostridium perfringens* is a highly resilient organism. While its vegetative cells can be killed at 65-70 °C under aerobic conditions, its spores can survive temperatures of up to 115 °C. Hence it is possible that spores that survived the hygienisation step can lead re-growth during the composting step.

Because there is no valid threshold for comparable products yet (e.g. biowaste compost or sewage sludge compost), it is recommended to further monitor *Clostridium perfringens* as a parameter for process optimisation without a fixed limit value. In case that elevated values occur in the final product, storing the faecal compost for at least 1 month before field application, appears to be a suitable measure to reduce the abundance of *Clostridium perfringens*. However, more data is needed to generalize this conclusion.

Organic pollutants

Aurin®: In general, the risk of organic pollutants occurring in Aurin® is low due to the activated-carbon filtration step. There is no obvious source for PAHs, dioxins and dl-PCBs in urine or percurine, as they typically arise from high-temperature processes such as combustion or pyrolysis. PFTs and per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) in general were found in human urine with varying total concentrations often in the range of a few ng/mL up to several hundred ng/mL (Nadal & Domingo, 2025). Concentrations in urine also strongly depend on the presence of a particular exposure, e.g. from industrial sites. Activated-carbon filtration can effectively remove PFAS if filters are properly maintained (Cserbik et al., 2023). Ultimately, more information is needed to determine whether PFAS pose a risk in urine-derived fertilisers. Therefore, PFTs are also analysed in the Aurin® fertiliser and its precursors within the P2Green project. Due to the lack of data and uncertainty of PFT limit values in liquid fertilisers, it is currently not possible to give a recommendation for an appropriate monitoring scheme. However, it is clear that PFAS should be prevented from entering the human body in the first place.

Faecal compost: PAHs are relevant if biochar is used as an additive, because they can be an unwanted byproduct from pyrolysis. In the 18 considered compost batches (17 batches from zirkulierBAR and first GE compost batch), PAHs were consistently below the limit value from DIN-SPEC 91421. Consequently, there is likely no particular risk from faecal compost. Often, the used biochar is already analysed for PAHs to get certification. In this case, it doesn't seem necessary to analyse the compost product (only if there was no analysis on biochar before). Dioxins and dl-PCBs are unintentional byproducts of combustion and industrial processes that can enter the human body via the food chain. In all 17 batches from zirkulierBAR, they were below the limit value. As mentioned above, dioxins and dl-PCBs were also not classified as an immediate risk by German local and national authorities. Therefore, the monitoring can follow the guidelines provided by RAL-GZ 251 (onetime analysis for classification recommended). PFTs were consistently below detection limit (<0.01 mg/kg DM) in the 18 considered faecal compost batches. Consequently, there is likely no particular risk from faecal compost. However, regular monitoring might still be necessary to comply with the requirements from local authorities.

Pharmaceutical residues

Aurin®: It has been shown that pharmaceutical residues can be efficiently removed during the urine treatment process (Duygan et al., 2021), with at least 90% reduction for all studied substances. Similar results were also found from the six sampling campaigns within the zirkulierBAR project (Krause et al., 2025). Furthermore, the activated-carbon filtration on nitrified urine was found to be more efficient than the removal of pharmaceutical residues in centralised wastewater treatment (Köpping et al., 2020). Hence pharmaceutical residues in Aurin® pose a minimal risk and regular monitoring is likely not necessary, with the current focus being to provide data from research and innovation projects to inform national and EU-level authorities.

Faecal compost: Potential pharmaceutical residues in faecal compost were also mentioned as a specific concern by German local and national authorities. The used dry toilet systems, where urine percolates through the solid parts, make it likely that also pharmaceutical residues excreted via urine are bound to the dry toilet contents used for producing the faecal compost fertiliser. The 17 compost batches analysed within the zirkulierBAR project showed variable concentrations of indicator substances (screening of 99 substances), with doxycycline being the most prevalent one with a maximum concentration of 0.11 mg/Kg DM in one batch. Most other indicator substances were often below detection limit. Additional analyses on the input materials for composting (dry toilet contents before and after hygienisation) also showed a strong decline during the composting step, especially for cotinine that was the most prevalent substance in the input material. Overall, the content of pharmaceutical residues found in faecal compost has been found to be several magnitudes lower than in sewage sludge (Häfner et al., 2023; Schinkel et al., 2025), with the latter being applied for decades on agricultural fields. In conclusion, pharmaceutical residues also do not pose a particular risk for faecal compost, and a regular monitoring is likely not necessary. However, a comprehensive

dataset created by research and innovation projects will help to alleviate concerns of a variety of stakeholders including public authorities, farmers and food consumers.

Phytohygiene

Aurin®: Not applicable.

Faecal compost: Only two batches out of the 18 considered batches included germinable plant parts or seeds, with the value being well-below the limit. This indicates that either the composting materials contain low amounts of germinable plant parts and seeds, or that they are sufficiently degraded during the composting process. In consequence, there is likely no risk in terms of phytohygiene. Regular quality assurance could be done based on RAL-GZ 251.

Finally, it should be noted that this risk assessment does not claim to be exhaustive, and, in case of doubt, the monitoring scheme and analysis parameters should be discussed with the local fertiliser authority.

- **Spanish pilot region**

Regulatory requirements for reclaimed water use

The use of reclaimed water for agricultural irrigation within the European Union is regulated by Regulation (EU) 2020/741, which establishes minimum quality requirements and monitoring obligations. In Spain, this framework is complemented by Royal Decree 1085/2024, which defines the legal regime for the reuse of treated wastewater.

For irrigation of woody crops through drip irrigation systems, the legislation specifies a set of maximum admissible values (MAV) and associated monitoring frequencies:

- *Escherichia coli*: $\leq 1,000$ CFU per 100 mL. A maximum deviation of up to one logarithmic unit is allowed, provided it does not occur in more than 10% of the samples collected within the monitoring period.
- Intestinal nematodes: ≤ 1 egg per 10 L. No deviation is permitted (100% of samples must comply with the MAV).
- Suspended solids (TSS): ≤ 35 mg/L. A maximum deviation of up to 100% of the MAV (i.e. up to 70 mg/L) is allowed, in no more than 10% of the samples collected within the monitoring period.

In addition to the microbiological and physical parameters, Spanish legislation requires the monitoring of *Legionella spp.* in irrigation systems where aerosols may be generated. Routine analysis of heavy metals and other potentially toxic elements is not mandated by law; however, in order to assess and prevent their potential long-term accumulation in soils and crops, a dedicated sampling campaign was carried out.

The monitoring strategy is structured according to the type of parameter and law:

- Weekly: microbiological indicators (*E. coli*, *Legionella spp.*, nematodes).
- Monthly: physico-chemical parameters (BOD₅, COD, TSS, electrical conductivity, pH, and nutrients).
- Monthly: heavy metals and other trace elements.

Compliance is evaluated over successive three-month monitoring periods and water is considered suitable for irrigation when all parameters remain below their MAVs, and when occasional exceedances do not surpass the admissible deviation limits nor represent more than 10% of the total number of samples within the period.

Heavy metals monitoring

All analyses performed in reclaimed water samples demonstrated that heavy metals, including arsenic, beryllium, cadmium, cobalt, chromium, copper, molybdenum, nickel, selenium, and vanadium were detected at concentrations several orders of magnitude below the reference thresholds established in scientific literature and guidelines for agricultural use (Hashem & Qi, 2021).

Table 23: Reference thresholds for heavy metals in irrigation water for agriculture and sampling mean obtained in reclaimed water at Spanish pilot region

Element	Long-Term Use (µg/L)*	Short-Term Use (µg/L)*	Sampling Mean (µg/L)
Arsenic (As)	100	2,000	3.90
Beryllium (Be)	100	500	1.00
Cadmium (Cd)	10	50	0.09
Cobalt (Co)	50	5,000	1.00
Chromium (Cr)	100	1,000	1.80
Copper (Cu)	200	5,000	5.96
Molybdenum (Mo)	10	50	2.30
Nickel (Ni)	200	2,000	2.55
Selenium (Se)	20	20	39.62**
Vanadium (V)	100	1,000	1.13

* *Long-Term Use*: For water used continuously on all soils.; *Short-Term Use*: For water used for a period less than 20 years. ** *Selenium* sample with a value of 471 was the only sample that exceeded the limits. If this sample is excluded, the average would be 0.41. No reasons have been found for this isolated spike.

Table 24: Historical data of heavy metals presence in reclaimed water at Spanish pilot region

Sampling Date	As	Be	Cd	Co	Cr	Cu	Mo	Ni	Se	V
Std. Dev.	6.7	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.6	2.6	1.2	0.9	1.2	0.1
Mean	3.90	1	0.09	1	1.80	5.96	2.30	2.55	0.76	1.13
Median	1.825	1	0.06	1	1.91	5.4	1.74	2.34	0.42	1.12
13/06/2023	1.85	1	0.06	1	1.25	4.69	1.62	2.11	0.49	1.2
12/07/2023	2.42	1	0.09	1	2.44	5.70	1.68	2.34	0.46	<1
23/08/2023	3.10	<1	0.27	<1	2.05	7.92	1.09	4.80	0.38	<1

18/09/2023	1.80	<1	0.06	<1	2.60	4.83	2.05	2.63	0.28	<1
11/10/2023	2.36	<1	0.03	<1	1.91	5.22	1.41	2.94	0.29	<1
08/11/2023	1.38	<1	0.06	<1	1.91	5.96	1.15	2.87	0.26	<1
13/12/2023	25.0	<1	0.08	<1	1.22	12.2	1.74	6.22	0.62	<1
16/01/2024	1.80	<1	<0.02	<1	<1	7.35	<1	1.64	447	<1
14/02/2024	1.52	<1	<0.02	<1	<1	5.40	2.35	1.52	0.35	<1
13/03/2024	2.43	<1	0.05	<1	<1	8.62	3.39	1.91	0.40	<1
10/04/2024	1.33	<1	<0.02	<1	<1	3.85	3.98	<2	0.45	<1
02/05/2024	1.75	<1	<0.02	<1	1	3.99	4.85	2.33	0.45	<1
12/06/2024	<5	<1	<0.05	<1	1.80	<5	<5	<2	<10	<1

Note: Any value preceded by the symbol "<" indicates that the concentration was below the analytical detection limit specified by the laboratory for that element.

As it can be observed, 100% of the analysed samples complied with the criteria for presence of heavy metals in water for irrigation in agriculture. After one year of monthly sampling, these results provided strong evidence that the use of reclaimed water does not pose risks of soil contamination or crop toxicity associated with the presence of heavy metals.

The favourable outcome of this monitoring effort also indicates that, from a regulatory perspective, the water source fulfils the requirements not only for microbiological quality but also for chemical safety, thereby reinforcing its suitability for sustainable agricultural irrigation.

Considerations on the optimisation of monitoring requirements

According to the Regulation (EU) 2020/741 and Royal Decree 1085/2024, the suitability of reclaimed water for irrigation is determined over successive three-month monitoring periods. Compliance is established when at least 90% of the samples collected within the period remain below the maximum admissible values (MAVs), and when occasional exceedances do not surpass the defined deviation limits. As a result, consistent compliance over time provides a statistically robust guarantee of water quality.

In the current monitoring program, a total of 28 nematode analyses and 21 *Legionella* spp. analyses have been performed, with 100% of the samples below detection limit, remaining below the reference thresholds.

On the basis of these results, and in alignment with the principle of risk-proportionate monitoring, it can be argued that, if a parameter consistently shows values far below its MAV across an extended monitoring period (e.g., ≥ 12 consecutive months of compliant results), the frequency of analysis for that parameter could be reduced or temporarily suspended. Such an adjustment would lead to a significant reduction in analytical costs, without compromising safety, as the long-term dataset provides strong evidence of negligible risk.

This proposal would need to be formally assessed and approved by the competent water authority. However, it represents a scientifically justified and economically efficient strategy, ensuring that monitoring resources can be prioritised towards parameters that display greater variability or higher potential risk.

Identified issues and proposed solutions

Although the monitoring programme (**Figure 33**) demonstrated overall compliance with regulatory requirements, several punctual deviations were recorded.

- *Escherichia coli*

The main difficulties were observed for *Escherichia coli*, where sporadic exceedances of the MAV (1,000 CFU 100 mL⁻¹) occurred. These deviations were not linked to a systematic inefficiency of the Water Reclamation Plant (tertiary treatment and disinfection process), but rather to mechanical incidents such as pump valve malfunctions or filter clogging due to filamentous algae proliferation in the municipal WWTP in sporadic cases. Corrective measures, including daily filter cleaning and the installation of an additional chlorination injection point, mitigated these peaks magnitude, frequency and improved compliance.

- Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD₅)

With regard to BOD₅, occasional exceedances were observed, particularly during the summer months of 2023 and early 2024, when values temporarily surpassed the admissible thresholds. These episodes were associated with fluctuations in the WWTP (secondary treated wastewater supplier) performance, often linked to seasonal variations in influent load.

Nevertheless, the marked reduction in both the frequency and the magnitude of BOD₅ peaks reduced after the installation of the second chlorination injection point. In the latter half of 2024 and throughout 2025, concentrations stabilized at values consistently close to zero.

- Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD)

The monitoring of COD revealed a similar pattern, with sporadic peaks above the expected range, especially in mid-2024. However, COD concentrations consistently remained within the regulatory standards.

- Total Suspended Solids (TSS)

Regarding TSS, most samples remained below the maximum admissible value (35 mg/L), with only a few isolated exceedances, such as the temporary peak detected in early 2024. Afterwards, operational protocols were reinforced with more regular filter cleaning. As a result, TSS concentrations showed a sustained downward trend, remaining well within the regulatory thresholds for almost the entire monitoring period.

To reduce future risks and further enhance the reliability of the reclaimed water system, three complementary solutions are proposed.

- Verification tank

The first solution consists of the installation of a large-capacity verification tank located downstream of the tertiary treatment and designed with the same specifications as the existing irrigation storage tanks.

In this system, reclaimed water would initially be directed into the verification tank, where it would be retained for a prudent period while undergoing laboratory analysis. Only once the results confirm that the batch complies with the maximum admissible values the water will be transferred into the irrigation tanks for agricultural use. Meanwhile, newly treated effluent would continue to enter the verification tank, maintaining a continuous cycle of storage, testing, and transfer. Although this approach requires additional storage capacity and introduces a short delay before the water can be applied in the field, it provides a robust safeguard by ensuring that no reclaimed water is used for irrigation until its quality has been analytically confirmed. In practice, this measure would significantly reduce uncertainty.

- *Escherichia coli* sensor

The second solution focuses on the incorporation of continuous monitoring sensors for critical parameters such as *Escherichia coli*.

The current monitoring programme is based exclusively on periodic sampling and laboratory analyses, which creates an unavoidable time gap between the moment reclaimed water is sampled and the moment results are available. During this interval, reclaimed water may already have been used, leaving uncertainty about its real-time quality. Sensors would mitigate this problem by providing immediate and continuous data, allowing operators to detect anomalies as they occur and to react without delay. In the event of an exceedance, contingency measures could be activated, such as temporarily diverting the effluent to a reserve tank, adjusting disinfection dosages, or switching to alternative water sources. While sensor-based monitoring does not replace laboratory testing for regulatory compliance, it greatly strengthens operational control, minimizes the risk of undetected exceedances.

- Disinfectant dosage

A third solution involves increasing the dosage of disinfectant applied to the reclaimed water by adjusting the injection ratio.

By supplying a higher concentration of disinfectant per litre of effluent, the system would strengthen its barrier against microbiological contamination, reducing the probability of *E. coli* exceedances and other pathogenic risks. This measure is relatively straightforward to implement from a technical perspective and can be adjusted according to water quality fluctuations and seasonal variations. When properly managed, the adjustment of

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disinfectant dosage offers a cost-effective and flexible strategy to enhance the robustness of the treatment process.

7 Conclusions

The results presented in this interim Deliverable 2.2 provide the most complete picture to date of the agroecological performance of P2GreenN's recycling fertilisers across the three pilot regions. Building on the methodological foundations established in D2.5 and incorporating the extended monitoring campaign performed between M24 and M36, this report demonstrates that the project is successfully generating robust, comparable and multi-dimensional datasets covering nutrient dynamics, plant and soil responses, water quality, hygiene indicators, contaminants of emerging concern, and environmental emissions.

Across all pilots, the monitoring efforts have confirmed that the variety of recycling fertilisers produced within P2GreenN—derived from source-separated human urine, faecal compost, and reclaimed municipal water—can be applied safely and effectively under field conditions. The data collected to M36 reveal that nutrient concentrations in the different fertiliser products are generally consistent with agronomic expectations, although natural variability between batches and pilot-specific processing conditions remains an important factor to be considered in the subsequent assessments. In parallel, the soil and plant monitoring conducted in Sweden, Germany and Spain shows positive or neutral agroecological effects when compared to conventional fertilisation practices, with no evidence to date of detrimental impacts on crop productivity or key soil indicators. Importantly, hygiene parameters and heavy metals have remained within acceptable thresholds, and while pharmaceuticals and other micropollutants have occasionally been detected—mainly associated with reclaimed water use—their concentrations have remained low and will continue to be closely monitored as the dataset increases.

The inclusion of risk assessment and sampling optimisation in this deliverable has strengthened the reliability of the monitoring framework. The identification of parameters that require higher sampling frequency, together with those that can be streamlined without compromising scientific robustness, will support more efficient data acquisition for the remaining period of Task 2.2. Furthermore, the consistent use of the standardised data collection sheets developed in T2.1 ensures that all results generated in the pilots are fully traceable and interoperable, facilitating future integration into the Impact Assessments (D2.3) and the policy and trade-off analyses (D2.4).

Overall, the findings presented in this interim report confirm that P2GreenN's pilot activities are progressing in line with expectations despite earlier delays requiring an extension of Task 2.2. The dataset collected so far provides a solid basis for evaluating the agronomic and environmental performance of circular fertilisers and for identifying areas where further refinement or validation may be needed. The final Deliverable 2.6, to be submitted in M44, will consolidate the complete 2.5-year monitoring dataset and provide the conclusive assessment of the agroecological impacts of recycling fertiliser application across the three pilot regions.

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